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Capstone Project

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JEEPNEY QUEUING AND TRACKING SYSTEM (JEEPQTS)

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Acceptance Page:

This paper prepared by **ROSEALE B. SOTTO** with the title: “**JEEPNEY QUEUING AND TRACKING SYSTEM (JEEPQTS)**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Course.

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Biographical Sketch

A Journey of Determination and Success

Roseale B. Sotto was born in the picturesque city of Baguio, Philippines, in October 1987, to proud parents Alberto and Carlina Sotto. From a young age, Roseale exhibited a curious mind and an unwavering determination to excel in life.

Her educational journey began at Saint Louis University in Baguio, where she pursued a Bachelor of Science in Electronics Engineering. Despite facing numerous challenges along the way, Roseale emerged victorious, overcoming obstacles with sheer perseverance and dedication. Her tenacity led her to pursue further studies, earning a Master of Information Systems from the prestigious University of the Philippines - Open University in Los Baños.

Roseale embarked on a career path that showcased her exceptional talents while taking her Master's Degree. She started her professional journey as a Product Engineer at Texas Instruments Philippines Inc. for 12 years, where she honed her skills and contributed significantly to the company's success. With her educational background solidified, her expertise and dedication caught the attention of industry leaders, paving the way for her current role as a Test Product Engineer at Advanced Semiconductor Engineering Singapore Pte Ltd.

Roseale's journey has been marked by challenges, but she has never allowed them to deter her spirit. Faced with the responsibility of providing for her family while striving to achieve her own dreams, she has emerged as a beacon of strength and resilience. Her personal traits of hard work, persistence, and resilience have not only propelled her forward but have also inspired those around her.

Known for her insatiable thirst for knowledge and her adventurous spirit, Roseale is never one to shy away from new opportunities or experiences. Her determination to succeed and her refusal to give up, even in the face of adversity, have earned her the respect and admiration of her peers.

Beyond her professional accomplishments, Roseale is renowned for her kindness and reliability. She is always willing to lend a helping hand and has become a trusted confidante to many.

As Roseale continues to forge ahead on her journey, she serves as a testament to the power of perseverance and the limitless potential of the human spirit. Her story inspires us all to pursue our dreams relentlessly and to never give up, no matter the odds.

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Dedicated to my parents:
Alberto L. Sotto and Carlina B. Sotto

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ABSTRACT

The lives of every individual around the world have started to shift to adapt to a digital environment. This need was further accelerated with the arrival of COVID 19 pandemic and have put a lot of pressure on different entities to rapidly shift their existing systems to a digital scheme. A lot were able to adjust quickly, specially those companies with dedicated Information Technology (IT) team in their organization. However, many other services need upgrading as well. One of these is the Transportation service.

An example of such are the Uber, Grab and Ankas services that were known to be effective in tracking and booking transportation services for Cabs, Cars, Motorcycles, etc. However, not everyone can afford to use these services as these transportation means are very expensive. The known public transportation in the Philippines are Jeepneys and yet, very little service providers resolve issues on Jeepney queuing. Different areas in the Philippines, have trouble in waiting for Jeepneys because they are either stuck on traffic, or parked because there's no way for drivers to know the demand for their services real time.

Thus, this project aims to provide an effective data gathering application to capture data needed both by jeepney drivers and passengers. It aims to provide real time view of the demand and available supply of jeepney transportation services across different areas at a cheaper cost. Both passengers and drivers do not need to spend money on mobile data, they can just use SMS messaging to upload and view information using the JeepQTS system.

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

A. Statement of the Problem

Public transportation provides people the mobility and access to employment, community resources, medical care, and recreational opportunities in communities. Different countries have their own public transportation services such as trains, bus and cabs since almost 90% of the population do not own a car. In first world countries, the public transportation were designed and developed in such a way that people can move smoothly esp. in times of emergency, public transportation is critical to safe and efficient evacuation, providing the resiliency that people needs in its emergency transportation network. Mobile applications are also available so that people can check schedules of buses and trains conveniently in their areas. The bus and train schedules are mostly accurate and effective since these were considered during their road designs and developments.

However, this kind of system is not applicable on most third world countries, like the Philippines. The road infrastructure are old and still under development, and the most common public transportation are Jeepney services. An application that is “schedule” based is not applicable in the Philippines. Usually, Jeepney drivers would like to make sure that vehicles are loaded with passengers before moving since this is still their source of income. Thus, the drivers will then either drive with fully loaded vehicle while leaving some passengers waiting on queue or under loaded but at the expense of the driver having lower profit gains.

Therefore, this makes it harder for both drivers and passengers as they don't have any means of checking the demand and supply of Jeepney services. Applications similar to Grab or Uber will not fit for this case as well since these are private booking applications and drivers will not be able to respond to all of its passengers.

B. Background and Objectives of the Project

This project will then address this concern and provide a real time data to drivers and passengers to obtain a better view of Jeepney service status. The goal of this project is to provide an effective data gathering system to capture data needed both by Jeepney drivers and passengers to provide real time view of the demand and available supply of Jeepney transportation services across different areas. Both passengers and drivers can use SMS messaging to upload and view information in the system. The system will not require GPS tracking devices for now since the goal is to implement the project at a lower cost and make use of the existing devices that most users have.

C. Significance and Scope of the Project

Most areas, esp. in the Provinces, that are using Jeepney as their mode of transportation, will benefit in this project if completed. A lot of provinces have fewer Jeepney vehicles that can accommodate people needing their services. They'll usually load their vehicles with passengers at the very start of their route and will no longer be able to accommodate other passengers waiting along the way. With this system, drivers will no longer need to worry if they can pick up passengers along the way since they can see it in the system, same thing for passengers who'd like to

contribute and inform the Jeepney operators by uploading data indicating that they're one of the passengers waiting for their services.

D. Documentation of Existence and Seriousness of the Problem

A research from the students Ateneo de Manila University stated in the "The Systemic Shortage in Philippine Public Transportation" that the Philippines has a massive public transportation shortage and this was made worse by the COVID 19 pandemic. The social distancing protocols have trimmed down the number of passengers that Jeepneys can carry and non-home based workers found it much harder to move and go to work (SWS, 2021).

E. Significance of the Study

The development of applications or data gathering systems for jeepney queuing in the Philippines holds substantial significance due to the following reasons:

- a) Optimizing Commuter Experience: Jeepneys serve as a primary mode of transportation for millions of Filipinos daily. Implementing a queuing system can streamline the boarding process, reducing wait times, and enhancing overall commuter experience. This not only improves convenience but also contributes to commuter safety and satisfaction.
- b) Efficiency in Public Transportation: By digitizing the queuing process, transportation authorities can effectively manage jeepney fleets, reducing congestion at terminals and improving route efficiency. This can lead to smoother traffic flow, reduced emissions, and ultimately, a more sustainable urban transportation system.

- c) Data-Driven Decision Making: The implementation of data gathering systems allows for the collection of valuable insights into commuter behavior, demand patterns, and operational efficiency. By analyzing this data, transportation authorities can make informed decisions regarding route planning, scheduling, and infrastructure development, leading to more effective resource allocation and service optimization.
- d) Enhancing Public Safety: Queuing systems can help enforce physical distancing measures, especially crucial during times of health crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic. By regulating passenger flow and capacity, these systems contribute to maintaining public safety and preventing the spread of infectious diseases within the transportation network.
- e) Empowering Local Communities: The development and deployment of technology-driven solutions for jeepney queuing empower local communities by fostering innovation and entrepreneurship. Local developers and businesses can contribute to the creation of these systems, leading to economic opportunities and skill development within the region.
- f) Addressing Urban Mobility Challenges: Urbanization and population growth in Philippine cities have resulted in increased pressure on existing transportation infrastructure. Implementing queuing systems for jeepneys addresses one aspect of urban mobility challenges, paving the way for a more efficient, inclusive, and sustainable transportation ecosystem.

In conclusion, the creation of applications or data gathering systems for jeepney queuing in the Philippines not only addresses immediate transportation needs but also contributes to broader socio-economic goals such as enhancing public safety, optimizing urban mobility, and fostering innovation. By leveraging

technology to improve commuter experience and transportation efficiency, this study has the potential to positively impact the lives of millions of Filipinos and shape the future of urban transportation in the country.

F. Scope and Limitation of the Study

Scope of the Study: This study aims to develop and evaluate the feasibility of applications or data gathering systems for jeepney queuing in the Philippines, focusing on the following key areas:

System Development: The study will involve the design, development, and implementation of software applications or data gathering systems tailored to the unique needs and context of jeepney queuing in Philippine urban environments.

User Interface Design: Special attention will be given to designing user-friendly interfaces that cater to the diverse demographic of jeepney commuters, considering factors such as literacy levels, language preferences, and technological proficiency.

Data Collection and Analysis: The study will explore various methods for collecting and analyzing queuing data, including passenger counts, boarding times, route utilization, and demographic information, to inform decision-making and system optimization.

Pilot Testing: Pilot testing of the developed applications or systems will be conducted in selected urban areas to assess usability, reliability, and effectiveness in real-world settings.

Limitations of the Study: Despite its scope, this study is subject to certain limitations:

Geographic Focus: The study will primarily focus on urban areas within the Philippines where jeepneys are a prevalent mode of transportation. Rural areas and regions with limited jeepney service may not be adequately represented.

Technological Infrastructure: The effectiveness of digital queuing systems is contingent upon the availability of reliable connectivity, SMS load balance and mobile devices among commuters. Areas with limited access to technology may not benefit fully from the proposed solutions.

Resource Constraints: The study may be limited by available resources, including funding, time, and technical expertise. As such, the scope of system development and implementation may be constrained by these factors.

Cultural and Behavioral Factors: Cultural norms, social dynamics, and commuter behaviors unique to the Philippines may influence the adoption and efficacy of digital queuing systems. These factors will be considered but may pose challenges in implementation and user acceptance.

Privacy and Security Concerns: The collection and handling of personal data within the queuing systems raise privacy and security concerns. The study will adhere to data protection regulations and implement measures to safeguard user privacy, but residual risks may remain.

Despite these limitations, this study seeks to make a valuable contribution to the field of urban transportation in the Philippines by exploring innovative solutions to improve commuter experience and system efficiency in jeepney queuing.

G. Operational definition of terminologies

Digital Environment: Refers to the technological landscape characterized by the widespread use and integration of digital technologies in various aspects of life, including communication, commerce, and services.

COVID-19 Pandemic: The global health crisis caused by the novel coronavirus, SARS-CoV-2, leading to widespread illness, mortality, and significant social and economic disruptions.

Information Technology (IT) Team: A dedicated group within an organization responsible for managing, maintaining, and implementing technology-related solutions and infrastructure to support the organization's objectives.

Transportation Service: The provision of means for individuals to travel from one location to another, including public transportation systems such as buses, trains, and jeepneys.

Jeepney: A popular mode of public transportation in the Philippines, typically consisting of modified jeeps or minivans used for commuting within cities and rural areas.

Queuing System: A system designed to manage and organize the waiting process, particularly in the context of transportation services, where passengers wait for available vehicles.

Data Gathering Application: An application designed to collect and compile relevant information from various sources, typically for analysis, decision-making, or monitoring purposes.

Real-Time View: Refers to the instantaneous display or updating of information as it occurs, providing users with up-to-date and accurate insights.

SMS Messaging: Short Message Service, a text messaging service that allows users to exchange short text messages via mobile phones.

GPS Tracking Devices: Global Positioning System technology used to determine the precise location of objects, such as vehicles, using satellite signals.

Urban Transportation: Refers to the movement of people and goods within urban areas, typically involving various modes of transportation and infrastructure.

CRUD: Create, Read, Update, Delete - Refers to the basic operations performed on data within a database management system.

OTP Verification: One-Time Password Verification - A security measure that uses a unique password generated for a single login session to verify the identity of users.

API Integration: Application Programming Interface Integration - The process of connecting different software applications to enable them to communicate and share data seamlessly.

Web Server: A server responsible for hosting websites and serving web pages to users over the internet.

Database Management System: Software used to manage and organize large volumes of data efficiently, typically including functions for data storage, retrieval, and manipulation.

Twilio: A cloud communications platform that provides APIs for integrating voice, SMS, and other communication services into applications.

Bootstrap: A front-end framework for developing responsive and mobile-first websites, providing pre-built CSS and JavaScript components.

Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP): The protocol used for transferring hypertext requests and information on the World Wide Web.

Client-Server Model: A distributed computing architecture where tasks or requests are divided between clients and servers, with servers providing resources or services to clients.

SMPP Protocol: Short Message Peer-to-Peer Protocol - A telecommunications industry protocol used for exchanging SMS messages between Short Message Service Centers and applications.

SSL: Secure Sockets Layer - A security protocol that establishes an encrypted link between a web server and a browser, ensuring secure data transmission over the internet.

Malware Scanner: Software designed to detect, remove, and prevent the spread of malicious software (malware) on computer systems.

Performance Requirements: Specifications outlining the expected performance characteristics and capabilities of a system, including speed, reliability, and scalability.

User Interface (UI) Design: The process of designing the visual layout and interactive elements of a software application or website to optimize user experience and usability.

Pilot Testing: A phase of testing conducted on a small scale or in a controlled environment to evaluate the feasibility, functionality, and user acceptance of a system or product before full-scale deployment.

Geographic Focus: The geographical areas or regions targeted or prioritized for attention, development, or implementation within a project or study.

Resource Constraints: Limitations imposed by available resources, such as funding, time, expertise, or infrastructure, that may impact the scope or execution of a project.

Cultural and Behavioral Factors: Social norms, customs, and behaviors that influence the adoption, acceptance, or effectiveness of a technology or intervention within a specific cultural context.

Privacy and Security Concerns: Issues related to the protection of personal data, confidentiality, and the prevention of unauthorized access or misuse of information within a system or application.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF EXISTING ALTERNATIVES

As of this writing, drivers get information if there are lots of passengers for pick-up through communication with other drivers and passengers only. Usually, people will point or inform the Jeepney operators what area they should pick up since some may have noted which areas have the long queue of waiting passengers. There are cases as well where dispatchers and drivers talk through transportable battery-operated radio but this is very rare since every driver should purchase one on their own. Others have attempted to developed mobile applications, but those applications will only guide new people on what route every Jeepney will pass through, it does not have any information about how drivers and passengers communicate or how high is the crowd of passengers or drivers waiting.

Most of the time, people will end up booking expensive transportation services on mobile applications like Uber, Grab, Ankas, etc. Almost everyone now have access to SMS messaging, but not all have Smartphones. Best option as of now is to utilize their devices and use it as a tool for a better data gathering system.

Chapter III

APPROACH TO BE TAKEN IN THIS PROJECT

A, Theoretical Framework

This project will mainly focus on Data Collection and Analysis Methods which employs a simple data collection and analysis method. It includes designing technological surveys or sensors to gather data on passenger queues, wait times, vehicle vacancy, and other relevant variables. It does not include statistical tools to analyze the collected data, to identify patterns and to derive insights for decision-making but it does provide and process a simple query to indicate status for the users. Other methods and theory considered was Urban Mobility and Sustainability with the use of the most common devices, cell phones through SMS technology which emphasizes the importance of accessibility. By integrating these perspectives into the framework, the project aims to contribute to the development of transportation solutions that are both efficient and environmentally responsible, aligning with broader sustainability goals.

B. Rationale for the Framework

The project's reliance on rigorous data collection and analysis methods is grounded in the belief that data-driven decision-making leads to more informed and effective outcomes. By collecting and analyzing relevant data, the project can identify patterns, trends, and areas for improvement, enabling stakeholders to make evidence-based decisions and allocate resources more efficiently. At the same time, The technology adoption framework underscores the importance of considering the needs, preferences, and behaviors of end-users when designing and implementing the data gathering system. By taking a user-centered approach, the project seeks to

enhance user acceptance and adoption, ultimately increasing the system's effectiveness and sustainability.

C. Technologies Used

The project was constructed using Bootstrap library (HTML, CSS, JS) during frontend web development and Twilio (REST) library for SMS API Integration. The backend web development however was built without framework and through native PHP programming language.

JeepQ Tracking System can be represented by the client-server model where the clients, such as the computer and cellphones, communicate to the server, web server and database, through the internet. The requests and responses are through Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP), protocol for fetching resources such as HTML documents and Short Message Peer-to-Peer (SMPP) Protocol, for exchanging SMS messages between Short Message Service Centers (SMSCs) and/or External Short Messaging Entities (ESMEs) or Application Programming Interface (API) to enable SMS messaging between applications and mobiles. This can be represented in Figure 5 Client-Server model.

Figure 1: Client-Server model

Performance Requirements:

Web Servers	: Apache Hostinger (online deployment)
	: Apache XAMPP (offline test)
Database	: MySQL DB Hostinger, MariaDB XAMPP
Frontend UI	: Bootstrap 5 by Spark (HTML, CSS, JS)
Backend	: PHP
SMS API	: Twilio Integration
Security	: SSL + Malware Scanner Hostinger
JeepQTS URL	: JeeqQ Tracking System (jeepqts.tech)
JeepQTS Number	: +639221101390

Chapter IV

PROJECT ASSESSMENT

A. Concept

The users of the JeepQ tracking system are the drivers, passengers and administrators who utilizes the Jeepney Services. JeepQTS will have its own database to store information about the number of queries sent to the application for transportation service requests including driver and vehicle information. It was developed to make transportation tracking easier specially for users (drivers and passengers) of Jeepney vehicles in rural and remote areas in the Philippines. Both the passenger and driver can perform real time input of data to the system, they can also perform query to view the status service requests. The administrator can be owned by the Barangay/City hall or group of the Jeepney Services who are in charge of updating the system information using web based application.

The user's system, for passengers and drivers, will be based on SMS applications and queries only. The web based applications are accessed by the administrators. Special features like precise map location, booking, and others are for future feature enhancements only and will not be discussed in this project. This is for the reason that the goal is to provide a more affordable query system that targets areas with low telecommunications signal. The users can inquire and query places where Jeepney services are needed, this is useful esp for cases where drivers are parked or stuck on traffic and a large queue of passengers are already waiting on specific areas. Not all areas can afford to use the cab or use the internet, hence, this system will introduce a solution to help areas in the Philippines to have a transportation tracking system for Jeepneys at a minimum cost.

Constraints include an easy to use interface that is web or mobile based application. It may also lack features like accessing precise locations. The queries and responses will be purely SMS based through API Integration. Also, this application may, or may not apply to other places, esp. outside Philippines.

This section presents a list of the fundamental sequence diagrams and use cases that satisfy the system's requirements, refer to Figure1 to Figure 4. The purpose is to provide an alternative, "structural" view of the requirements stated above and how they might be satisfied in the system.

Operating Scenarios:

Scenario A: Administration Initial Area / Route Registration

The user (Admin) shall enter the information about the area and routes into the database for its initial construction and evolution. The fields will be completed via a form that will manipulate the data. Administration can update/delete invalid registrations. All time, routes, locations will be predefined for now while the system has no precise map location.

Scenario B: Passenger and Driver Registration

The user (Passenger / Driver) shall be able to enter information about their details, and record this into the database. Each person can only register once using their unique cell number and National ID number. The user can alter / delete her own information through SMS messaging.

Scenario C: Passenger and Driver Data Upload / Download

The user (Passenger / Driver) can upload information about their location, time and actions like "Waiting for passenger @PlaceA", "Waiting for Jeepney

@PlaceB”, “Left @TimeA and now Driving on @Route”, etc. The users can alter/delete information after the service has been provided, else, a predefined timer will close the service requests to avoid wrong information during queries.

Use Case Model

Figure 2: Use case model of JeepQ Tracking System

Sequence Diagrams

Actor: Administration

Figure 3 : Sequence diagram for creating new route and user registration as well

Actor: Passenger / Administration

Figure 4 : Sequence diagram for Passenger Upload or Query service requests

Actor: Driver / Administration

Figure 5 : Sequence diagram for Driver Upload or Query requests

B. Methods

a. System Features

JeepQTS system ensures that proper access are granted to different users, customer have a way to register both web and sms and that routes can be uploaded and maintained. The functions of such features are discussed and illustrated mor in this section.

System Login Registration and Update:

This feature enables CRUD (create, create, read, update and delete) of providing access to users in the web application, refer to Figure 6. There are only 2 access, that's "administrator" which has the CRUD access of all features and "user" who has Read access only on specific pages. The update feature however will not

be able to store previous information and will immediately update on the fly without logging previous values. Only administrators can access and use this page.

Figure 6 : User access page sample

User Registration and Update (Web and SMS)

This feature enables registration of both drivers and passengers using either Web application or SMS registration. The web application is also equipped with CRUD feature to provide seamless maintenance of all subscribers or customers of the system. “Administrator” accounts can access the whole CRUD feature where as the “user” accounts can only view the list and some details but will not be able to perform any creation, update or deletion. Refer to Figure 7 for sample details.

Figure 7 : Sample page and screenshots of subscriber registrations

OTP Verification

This feature is to incorporate SMS OTP verification during web application registration to ensure that correct mobile numbers are registered for each individual. Refer to Figure 8 for sample. Only administrators can access this feature.

Figure 8 : OTP Verification sample of JeepQTS

Route Registration and Update

This page is similar to subscriber registration with CRUD feature but for this case, it will record the places and Jeepney routes that will be used as reference for SMS Query. Only administrators can perform the whole CRUD feature, users will only be able to view this page. Refer to Figure 9.

Figure 9 : Route CRUD page sample of JeepQTS

SMS Messaging

Lastly, another system feature is to use SMS messaging to both communicate and to use as a tool for the upload and query. Kindly refer to Figure 10 for sample snapshots and Appendix for the list of commands that can be used in the system

Figure 10: Sample SMS Messaging Feature of JeepQTS

b. Database Design

The JeepQTS database is composed of tables that are used in the whole system, refer to Figure 11. Most of these tables stores information of registered entries from the JeepQTS system. Brief description of the tables are the following:

jeepq_users - Login details for the website's access

jeepq_list - Users registered in the system

verification - OTP codes for users registered through the website

routes - Registered jeepney routes

sms_query - raw and processed data received from SMS API

jeepq_data - decision making data used for both query and uploads

Figure 11: JeepQTS Database Model

c. Implementation

JeepQ Tracking System was initially deployed at AWS EC2 Instance but since the monthly maintenance is too high and due to its complexity, it was then fully deployed at Hostinger hosting server. The SMS Integration was also moved from Globe API to Twilio due to wide source of information during development. A detailed status and timeline of implementation is shown on Tables 1 and 2.

Activities	When	Status
Research and Learn PHP Backend and HTML, CSS, JS Frontend online. Study AWS server deployment for Dynamic websites	April wk1-wk3,2022	Done
Create Registration database	April 30,2022	Done
Create Admin and User Login Sessions/Priveleges	May 1, 2022	Done
Create Registration and Viewing Page (CRUD)		Done
- Add Entries	May 7, 2022	Done
- View Entries	May 8, 2022	Done
- Edit Entries	May 14, 2022	Done
- Delete Entries	May 15, 2022	Done
Create AWS EC2 account for Web Hosting	May 21,2022	Done
SMS API Integration Globelabs	May 22, 2022	Done
-Subscribe+Save in Database	May 27, 2022	Done
-Unsubscribe+Delete in Database	May 28, 2022	Done

Table 1: JeepQTS Timeline at the start of development

Activities	When	Status
SMS API Integration Twilio - Learn from Udemy (Migrate to Twilio due to difficulties / issues encountered in Globelabs)	April 15, 2023	Done
- Send message from web application to SMS	April 22, 2023	Done
- Cell number / Passenger registration with Verification (OTP Like)	April 29,2023	Done
Migrate from AWS EC2 to Hostinger (Due to AWS acct got hacked and complex process), setup jeepqts.tech Domain	May 6, 2023	Done
- Receive messages (using Philippine numbers to Test)	May 7, 2023	Done
- Learn and create chatbot sample	May 13,2023	Done
Migrate frontend to bootstrap format for CRUD of passengers and driver form	May 14,2023	Done
- Registration of users - completed for passengers only, both through web and sms registration	May 20, 2023	Done
- Record user queries from sms messages	May 21, 2023	Done
- Registration and CRUD for web app user access	May 27, 2023	Done
- Create data tables needed for routes	May 28, 2023	Done
- Migrate to bootstrap format CRUD for route updates	June 3, 2023	Done
- Receive and autoreply SMS queries using chatbot concept	June 4, 2023	Done
Presentation	June 9, 2023	Done

Table 2 : Finalized JeepQTS development timeline

C. Plan for User Testing and Project Assessment

The system was composed of frontend and backend development. Initially, development was performed on basic HTML, CSS, Javascript and PHP core languages to ensure that login sessions and CRUD (create, read, update and delete) functions are properly coded. This was through basic text editor “Atom”, XAMPP “Apache” and “MySQL” local server and through regular web browsers. Most of the testing was done manually by testing the features through web browsers and update the codes real time depending on the expected and actual results.

After completing a fully function CRUD web application, the next development was to search for a hosting site. Initially, AWS was the chosen web server, however,

developer have moved to Hostinger (including domain purchase) due to its simplicity and affordability. The reason why web hosting and deployment was done first is to be able to test the next feature which is SMS integration.

Next is the SMS Integration, wherein Globelabs API was used but due to lack of available online resources about Globelabs API and since the developer is unfamiliar of SMS API Integration, it moved to Twilio SMS API app as its lessons and discussions is more abundant online about this Application. The sequence of development is the SMS sending feature, Registration, OTP feature, SMS receiving and Auto reply features. Testing was performed using both overseas (Singapore) and local (Philippine) cellular numbers. The developer have remotely access here mother's cellphone through Team Viewer for certain nights to be able to continue coding, test and debug the SMS feature of this system. This is the feature where the developer struggled as she is not familiar with this technology and she doesn't have a cheaper access to cellular number that can be used during development at a cheaper cost. Eventually, the developer decided to go home to Philippines to be able to continue and finish most of the important SMS messaging features.

Lastly, was the creation of the whole system by integrating all the designed functions and database using the Bootstrap template. Most of the errors and the bugs were caught using the manual trail and error method. At the end of the development, the developer have requested her family members to test and register through the system and have later used some testing sites to further check for some bugs and security issues.

One of the testing sites or application used is the Lighthouse Chrome extension which is used to test overall performance of a website. Figure 12 shows the result of the JeepQTS website.

Figure 12: Lighthouse Report Result of JeepQTS System

Performance - A website experience free of friction and disruptions is an absolute must for improving conversion rates, generating more leads, and increasing revenue.

Accessibility - These checks highlight opportunities to improve the accessibility of the web app. Only a subset of accessibility issues can be automatically detected so manual testing is still important.

Best Practices - Includes best approaches used in the web application.

SEO These checks ensure that the page is following basic search engine optimization advice. There are many additional factors Lighthouse does not score There that may affect your search ranking, including performance on Core Web Vitals.

Security Testing

The tool used to test the security of your system is <https://www.zaproxy.org/>. Manual testing was also performed by accessing individual files using URL bar and ensuring that these are not accessible without proper login sessions. Result of ZAP scanning is shown on Figure 13-14.

ZAP Scanning Report

Site: <https://jeepqts.tech>

Generated on Tue, 13 Jun 2023 00:03:09

ZAP Version: 2.12.0

Summary of Alerts

Risk Level	Number of Alerts
High	0
Medium	5
Low	5
Informational	2

Figure 13: ZAP Scanning Report Summary

Alerts

Name	Risk Level	Number of Instances
Absence of Anti-CSRF Tokens	Medium	2
CSP: Wildcard Directive	Medium	4
CSP: script-src unsafe-inline	Medium	4
CSP: style-src unsafe-inline	Medium	4
Missing Anti-clickjacking Header	Medium	2
Cookie No HttpOnly Flag	Low	1
Cookie without SameSite Attribute	Low	1
Server Leaks Information via "X-Powered-By" HTTP Response Header Field(s)	Low	2
Strict-Transport-Security Header Not Set	Low	12
X-Content-Type-Options Header Missing	Low	10
Information Disclosure - Suspicious Comments	Informational	1
Modern Web Application	Informational	4

Figure 14: ZAP Scanning Report Details

Chapter V

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Web application development, deployment, database management and SMS API Integration are all new to the the author/developer. The JeepQTS project made the developer realize that she is capable of developing such system. This is the first web application system she has ever developed. It is totally different from the field she is currently working on as an Engineer but the project have totally upscaled her skills in terms of web application development. The SMS API Integration is one of the most challenging part of JeepQTS development as the developer have a very minimal knowledge on web development. It was a very long journey that she almost quit, but because of the plenteous amount of resources online, patience and perseverance in studying have helped the developer accomplish such milestone.

However, investments have to be incorporated to ensure that the whole system will function seamlessly. This will somewhat hinder the system maintenance as most of which will have expiration such as Twilio number renewal and Hostinger web server plan. The developer however will try to sustain the Hostinger server plan to see if this can be utilized for future web development projects.

Chapter VI

CONCLUSION

With the right determination to learn, everyone is capable of accomplishing anything. This is true for this project, with various sources available, students just need patience and perseverance to understand and work on their goals.

JeepQ Tracking System can be a good start to improve the overall Public Transportation systems in the Philippines. The ultimate goal is to convert into a Train or Bus system, but it's still the same queuing and data gathering problem. JeepQTS can be improved by adding feature to auto detect location during upload. It can be through mobile application as well.

Chapter VII

RECOMMENDATIONS

It would help if the different types of API integration be taught through classroom projects for individual students of the Masters of Information Systems to aid everyone about this technology.

REFERENCES

JEEPNEY TRANSPORTATION : <https://www.fhwa.dot.gov/policy/2002cpr/pdf/ch14.pdf>

BASIC PHP TUTORIAL:

<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLKyjE37ORK3LL6U2z3mz4fEuaM9VFp28H>

SMS API TWILIO SEND SMS WITH OTP VERIFY: <https://www.udemy.com/course/php-send-and-receive-mobile-text-messages-sms/>

SMS API TWILIO RECEIVE SMS: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GTDAI71V37A&t=99s>

CHAT BOT: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tQKG5r9MwRU&t=7s>

BOOTSTRAP CONVERSION: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=O_9u1P5YjVc

SMS API: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YrfhPILUuwA>

CLIENT SERVER MODEL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Client%E2%80%93server_model

APPENDICES

APPENDIX A User Manual

Download Complete Codes: <https://jeepqts.tech/jeepqts3.tar.gz>

JeepQTS URL [expired] : [JeeqQ Tracking System \(jeepqts.tech\)](http://JeeqQ Tracking System (jeepqts.tech))

JeepQTS Number [expire] : +639221101390

JeepQTS SMS Codes:

Here are the common codes for JeepQ Tracking System:

JHELP - Guide for common codes on JeepQ System (i.e. JHELP)

REG - Register in the system (i.e. REG Firstname Lastname Gender Location Birthdate)

JEEPQTS - All JeepQ Upload and Query Commands followed by

[WAIT DRIVE PQUERY DQUERY]

WAIT - for Passengers and Drivers to upload their Queue request with Location (i.e. JEEPQTS WAIT Location RouteLetter JeepStopNumber)

DRIVE - for Drivers to indicate that they're now driving on route (i.e. JEEPQTS DRIVE)

PQUERY - for all users to inquire how many passengers are waiting per route/location (i.e. JEEPQTS PQUERY)

DQUERY - for all users to inquire how many drivers are on route and how many are available (i.e. JEEPQTS DQUERY)

SUPPORT - Send message to Admin for Customer support (i.e. SUPPORT Message)

APPENDIX B
Complete Program Listing

add.php

```

<?php

include_once("connections/connections.php");
$con = connection();

if(!isset($_SESSION)){
    session_start();
}
if(!isset($_SESSION['UserLogin'])){
    echo header("Location: index.php");
}else{

if(isset($_POST['submit_input'])){

    $fname = strtoupper($_POST['firstname']);
    $lname = strtoupper($_POST['lastname']);
    $birthday = $_POST['birthday'];
    $gender = strtoupper($_POST['gender']);
    $location = strtoupper($_POST['location']);
    $number = $_POST['number'];
    $role = strtoupper($_POST['role']);
    $plate_num= strtoupper($_POST['plate_num']);

    $sql = "INSERT INTO `jeepq_list`(`first_name`, `last_name`,
`birth_day`, `gender`, `location`, `cell_number`, `verif_status`, `role`, `plate_num`) VALUES
('$fname', '$lname', '$birthday', '$gender', '$location', '$number', '0', '$role', '$plate_num')";
    $con->query($sql) or die($con->error);
    echo header("Location: passenger-details.php"); //redirects page to avoid double entry uploads
}
}

?>

<?php include "header.php";?>

</nav>
<main class="content">
<div class="container-fluid">

<div class="header">
<h1 class="header-title">
Add New Subscribers
</h1>
<nav aria-label="breadcrumb">
<ol class="breadcrumb">
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Home</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Accounts</a></li>

```

```

<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="passenger-details.php">Passenger List</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item active" aria-current="page">Add New Subscribers</li>
</ol>
</nav>
</div>

```

```

<div class="card">
<div class="card-header">

<h5 class="card-title mb-0">Private info</h5>
</div>
<div class="card-body">
<form action="" method="post">
<div class="row">
<div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
<label>First name</label>
<input type="text" class="form-control" name="firstname" id="firstname" placeholder="First
name">
</div>
<div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
<label>Last name</label>
<input type="text" class="form-control" name="lastname" id="lastname" placeholder="Last
name">
</div>
</div>
<div class="row">
<div class="mb-3 col-md-3">
<label>Gender</label>
<select class="form-select flex-grow-1" name="gender" id="select">
<option value="">Select...</option>
<option value="MALE">MALE</option>
<option value="FEMALE">FEMALE</option>
</select>
</div>
<div class="mb-3 col-md-3">
<label>Location</label>
<select class="form-select flex-grow-1" name="location" id="select">
<option value="">Select...</option>
<option value="BAGUIO">BAGUIO</option>
<option value="TRINIDAD">TRINIDAD</option>
</select>
</div>
<div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
<label>Birth Date</label>
<input class="form-control" type="date" name="birthday" id="birthday"/>
</div>
</div>
<div class="mb-3">

```

```

<div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
<label>Cell Number</label>
<input type="text" class="form-control" maxlength="13" name="number" id="number"
placeholder="+63 Number" value="+63">
</div>
</div>
<div class="row">
<div class="mb-3 col-md-3">
<label>Role</label>
<select onchange="yesnoCheck(this);" class="form-select flex-grow-1" name="role" id="select">
<option value="">Select...</option>
<option value="PASSENGER">PASSENGER</option>
<option value="DRIVER">DRIVER</option>
</select>
</div>
<div class="mb-3 col-md-3" id="ifYes" style="display: none;">
<label for="car">Plate Number</label>
<input type="text" class="form-control" id="plate_num"
name="plate_num" /><br />
</div>
</div>
<input type="button" class="btn btn-primary"
onclick="document.location='passenger-details.php'" value="Back">
<button type="submit" class="btn btn-primary" name="submit_input" value="Submit
Form">Submit</button>
</form>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</main>
<footer class="footer">
<div class="container-fluid">
<div class="row text-muted">
<div class="col-8 text-start">
<ul class="list-inline">
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Support</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Privacy</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Terms of Service</a>
</li>

```

```

<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Contact</a>
</li>
</ul>
</div>
<div class="col-4 text-end">
<p class="mb-0">
&copy; 2022 - <a href="dashboard-default.html" class="text-muted">Spark</a>
</p>
</div>

```

```

<svg width="0" height="0" style="position:absolute">
<defs>
<symbol viewBox="0 0 512 512" id="ion-ios-pulse-strong">
<path
d="M448 273.001c-21.27 0-39.296 13.999-45.596 32.999h-38.857l-28.361-85.417a15.999 15.999 0 0-15.183-10.956c-.112 0-.224 0-.335.004a15.997 15.997 0 0 0-15.049 11.588l-44.484 155.262-52.353-314.108C206.535 54.893 200.333 48 192 48s-13.693 5.776-15.525 13.135L115.496 306H16v31.999h112c7.348 0 13.75-5.003 15.525-12.134l45.368-182.177 51.324 307.94c1.229 7.377 7.397 11.92 14.864 12.344.308.018.614.028 7.097 0 13.406-3.701 15.381-10.594l49.744-173.617 15.689 47.252A16.001 16.001 0 0 0 352 337.999h51.108C409.973 355.999 427.477 369 448 369c26.511 0 48-22.492 48-49 0-26.509-21.489-46.999-48-46.999z">
</path>
</symbol>
</defs>
</svg>
<script src="js/app.js"></script>

```

```

<script type="text/javascript">
function yesnoCheck(that) {
  if (that.value == "DRIVER") {
    alert("Input your Jeepney's plate number.");
    document.getElementById("ifYes").style.display = "block";
  } else {
    document.getElementById("ifYes").style.display = "none";
  }
}
</script>
</body>

</html>

```

chat.php

```

<?php
//checks if the session already set

```

```

if(!isset($_SESSION)){
    session_start();
}

if(!isset($_SESSION['UserLogin'])){
    echo header("Location: login.php");
}

include_once("connections/connections.php"); //para hnd paulit ulit na include
$con = connection(); //requesting connection to database
?>

<?php include "header.php";?>

</nav>
<main class="content">
<div class="container-fluid">

<div class="header">
<h1 class="header-title">
Chat
</h1>
<nav aria-label="breadcrumb">
<ol class="breadcrumb">
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="dashboard-default.html">Dashboard</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="#">Pages</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item active" aria-current="page">Chat</li>
</ol>
</nav>
</div>
<div class="card">
<div class="row g-0">
<div class="col-12 col-lg-5 col-xl-3 border-end">

<div class="px-4 d-none d-md-block">
<div class="d-flex align-items-center">
<div class="flex-grow-1">
<input type="text" class="form-control my-3" placeholder="Search...">
</div>
</div>
</div>

<a href="#" class="list-group-item list-group-item-action border-0">
<div class="badge bg-success float-end">5</div>
<div class="d-flex align-items-start">

<div class="flex-grow-1 ms-3">
Michelle Bilodeau

```

```

<div class="small"><span class="fas fa-circle chat-online"></span> Online</div>
</div>
</div>
</a>
<a href="#" class="list-group-item list-group-item-action border-0">
<div class="badge bg-success float-end">2</div>
<div class="d-flex align-items-start">

<div class="flex-grow-1 ms-3">
Alexander Groves
<div class="small"><span class="fas fa-circle chat-online"></span> Online</div>
</div>
</div>
</a>
<a href="#" class="list-group-item list-group-item-action border-0">
<div class="d-flex align-items-start">

<div class="flex-grow-1 ms-3">
Kathie Burton
<div class="small"><span class="fas fa-circle chat-online"></span> Online</div>
</div>
</div>
</a>
<a href="#" class="list-group-item list-group-item-action border-0">
<div class="d-flex align-items-start">

<div class="flex-grow-1 ms-3">
Daisy Seger
<div class="small"><span class="fas fa-circle chat-offline"></span> Offline</div>
</div>
</div>
</a>
<a href="#" class="list-group-item list-group-item-action border-0">
<div class="d-flex align-items-start">

<div class="flex-grow-1 ms-3">
Fiona Green
<div class="small"><span class="fas fa-circle chat-offline"></span> Offline</div>
</div>
</div>
</a>
<a href="#" class="list-group-item list-group-item-action border-0">
<div class="d-flex align-items-start">

<div class="flex-grow-1 ms-3">
Doris Wilder

```

```

<div class="small"><span class="fas fa-circle chat-offline"></span> Offline</div>
</div>
</div>
</a>
<a href="#" class="list-group-item list-group-item-action border-0">
<div class="d-flex align-items-start">

<div class="flex-grow-1 ms-3">
Haley Kennedy
<div class="small"><span class="fas fa-circle chat-offline"></span> Offline</div>
</div>
</div>
</a>
<a href="#" class="list-group-item list-group-item-action border-0">
<div class="d-flex align-items-start">

<div class="flex-grow-1 ms-3">
Jennifer Chang
<div class="small"><span class="fas fa-circle chat-offline"></span> Offline</div>
</div>
</div>
</a>

<hr class="d-block d-lg-none mt-1 mb-0" />
</div>
<div class="col-12 col-lg-7 col-xl-9">
<div class="py-2 px-4 border-bottom d-none d-lg-block">
<div class="d-flex align-items-center py-1">
<div class="position-relative">

</div>
<div class="flex-grow-1 ps-3">
<strong>Kathie Burton</strong>
<div class="text-muted small"><em>Typing...</em></div>
</div>
<div>
<button class="btn btn-primary btn-lg me-1 px-3"><i class="feather-lg" data-
feather="phone"></i></button>
<button class="btn btn-info btn-lg me-1 px-3 d-none d-md-inline-block"><i class="feather-lg"
data-feather="video"></i></button>
<button class="btn btn-light border btn-lg px-3"><i class="feather-lg" data-feather="more-
horizontal"></i></button>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>

<div class="position-relative">
<div class="chat-messages p-4">

```

```

<div class="chat-message-right pb-4">
<div>

<div class="text-muted small text-nowrap mt-2">2:33 am</div>
</div>
<div class="flex-shrink-1 bg-light rounded py-2 px-3 me-3">
<div class="fw-bold mb-1">You</div>
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, vis erat denique in, dicunt prodesset te vix.
</div>
</div>

```

```

<div class="chat-message-left pb-4">
<div>

<div class="text-muted small text-nowrap mt-2">2:34 am</div>
</div>
<div class="flex-shrink-1 bg-light rounded py-2 px-3 ms-3">
<div class="fw-bold mb-1">Kathie Burton</div>
Sit meis deleniti eu, pri vidit meliore docendi ut, an eum erat animal commodo.
</div>
</div>

```

```

<div class="chat-message-right mb-4">
<div>

<div class="text-muted small text-nowrap mt-2">2:35 am</div>
</div>
<div class="flex-shrink-1 bg-light rounded py-2 px-3 me-3">
<div class="fw-bold mb-1">You</div>
Cum ea graeci tractatos.
</div>
</div>

```

```

<div class="chat-message-left pb-4">
<div>

<div class="text-muted small text-nowrap mt-2">2:36 am</div>
</div>
<div class="flex-shrink-1 bg-light rounded py-2 px-3 ms-3">
<div class="fw-bold mb-1">Kathie Burton</div>
Sed pulvinar, massa vitae interdum pulvinar, risus lectus porttitor magna, vitae commodo lectus
mauris et velit.
Proin ultricies placerat imperdiet. Morbi varius quam ac venenatis tempus.
</div>
</div>

```

```

<div class="chat-message-left pb-4">
<div>

<div class="text-muted small text-nowrap mt-2">2:37 am</div>
</div>
<div class="flex-shrink-1 bg-light rounded py-2 px-3 ms-3">
<div class="fw-bold mb-1">Kathie Burton</div>
Cras pulvinar, sapien id vehicula aliquet, diam velit elementum orci.
</div>
</div>

```

```

<div class="chat-message-right mb-4">
<div>

<div class="text-muted small text-nowrap mt-2">2:38 am</div>
</div>
<div class="flex-shrink-1 bg-light rounded py-2 px-3 me-3">
<div class="fw-bold mb-1">You</div>
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, vis erat denique in, dicunt prodesset te vix.
</div>
</div>

```

```

<div class="chat-message-left pb-4">
<div>

<div class="text-muted small text-nowrap mt-2">2:39 am</div>
</div>
<div class="flex-shrink-1 bg-light rounded py-2 px-3 ms-3">
<div class="fw-bold mb-1">Kathie Burton</div>
Sit meis deleniti eu, pri vidit meliore docendi ut, an eum erat animal commodo.
</div>
</div>

```

```

<div class="chat-message-right mb-4">
<div>

<div class="text-muted small text-nowrap mt-2">2:40 am</div>
</div>
<div class="flex-shrink-1 bg-light rounded py-2 px-3 me-3">
<div class="fw-bold mb-1">You</div>
Cum ea graeci tractatos.
</div>
</div>

```

```

<div class="chat-message-right mb-4">
<div>

```

```


<div class="text-muted small text-nowrap mt-2">2:41 am</div>
</div>
<div class="flex-shrink-1 bg-light rounded py-2 px-3 me-3">
<div class="fw-bold mb-1">You</div>
Morbi finibus, lorem id placerat ullamcorper, nunc enim ultrices massa, id dignissim metus urna eget
purus.
</div>
</div>

```

```

<div class="chat-message-left pb-4">
<div>

<div class="text-muted small text-nowrap mt-2">2:42 am</div>
</div>
<div class="flex-shrink-1 bg-light rounded py-2 px-3 ms-3">
<div class="fw-bold mb-1">Kathie Burton</div>
Sed pulvinar, massa vitae interdum pulvinar, risus lectus porttitor magna, vitae commodo lectus
mauris et velit.
Proin ultricies placerat imperdiet. Morbi varius quam ac venenatis tempus.
</div>
</div>

```

```

<div class="chat-message-right mb-4">
<div>

<div class="text-muted small text-nowrap mt-2">2:43 am</div>
</div>
<div class="flex-shrink-1 bg-light rounded py-2 px-3 me-3">
<div class="fw-bold mb-1">You</div>
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, vis erat denique in, dicunt prodesset te vix.
</div>
</div>

```

```

<div class="chat-message-left pb-4">
<div>

<div class="text-muted small text-nowrap mt-2">2:44 am</div>
</div>
<div class="flex-shrink-1 bg-light rounded py-2 px-3 ms-3">
<div class="fw-bold mb-1">Kathie Burton</div>
Sit meis deleniti eu, pri vidit meliore docendi ut, an eum erat animal commodo.
</div>
</div>

```

```

</div>
</div>

```



```

7.397 11.92 14.864 12.344.308.018.614.028.919.028 7.097 0 13.406-3.701 15.381-10.594|49.744-
173.617 15.689 47.252A16.001 16.001 0 0 0 352 337.999h51.108C409.973 355.999 427.477 369 448
369c26.511 0 48-22.492 48-49 0-26.509-21.489-46.999-48-46.999z">
</path>
</symbol>
</defs>
</svg>
<script src="js/app.js"></script>

<script>
// Chat
document.addEventListener("DOMContentLoaded", function() {
$('.chat-messages').scrollTop($('.chat-messages')[0].scrollHeight);
});
</script>
</body>

</html>

```

delete.php

```

<?php

include_once("connections/connections.php");
$con = connection();

//echo $_POST['IDdelete'];
//print_r($_POST);

if(!isset($_SESSION)){
    session_start();
}

if(!isset($_SESSION['UserLogin'])){
    echo header("Location: index.php");
}else{

if(isset($_POST['delete_button'])){

    $iddelete = $_POST['IDdelete'];
    $sql = "DELETE FROM jeepq_list WHERE id ='$iddelete";
    $con->query($sql) or die ($con->error);

    echo header("Location: passenger-details.php");
}
}
?>

```

details.php

```

<?php
//checks if the session already set

```

```
include_once("connections/connections.php"); //para hnd paulit ulit na include
$con = connection(); //requesting connection to database
```

```
if(!isset($_SESSION)){
    session_start();
}
```

```
if(!isset($_SESSION['UserLogin'])){
    echo header("Location: index.php");
}else{
```

```
$idview = $_GET['IDview'];
```

```
$sql = "SELECT * FROM jeepq_list WHERE id = '$idview'";
$students = $con->query($sql) or die($con->error);
$row = $students->fetch_assoc(); // retrieves 1 only (need loop statements)
```

```
}
```

```
// if(isset($_POST['update_input'])){
//
//     $fname = $_POST['firstname'];
//     $lname = $_POST['lastname'];
//     $birthday = $_POST['birthday'];
//     $gender = $_POST['gender'];
//     $location = $_POST['location'];
//     $number = '+63' . $_POST['number'];
//
//     $sql = "UPDATE jeepq_list SET first_name='$fname', last_name='$lname', gender='$gender',
birth_day='$birthday', location='$location', cell_number='$number' WHERE id='$idedit'";
//     $con->query($sql) or die($con->error);
//
//     echo header("Location: details.php?IDview=".$idedit); //redirects page to avoid double entry
uploads
// }
```

```
?>
```

```
<?php include "header.php";?>
```

```
</nav>
```

```
<main class="content">
```

```
<div class="container-fluid">
```

```
<div class="header">
```

```
<h1 class="header-title">
```

```
View Subscriber Details
```

```

</h1>
<nav aria-label="breadcrumb">
<ol class="breadcrumb">
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Home</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Accounts</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="passenger-details.php">Subscribers</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item active" aria-current="page">View Subscriber Details</li>
</ol>
</nav>
</div>

```

```

<div class="card">
  <div class="card-header">

    <h5 class="card-title mb-0">Private info</h5>
  </div>
  <div class="card-body">
    <form action="delete.php" method="post">
      <div class="row">
        <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
          <label>First name</label>
          <input type="text" class="form-control" name="firstname" id="firstname" value="<?php
echo $row['first_name'];?>" readonly>
        </div>
        <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
          <label>Last name</label>
          <input type="text" class="form-control" name="lastname" id="lastname" value="<?php
echo $row['last_name'];?>" readonly>
        </div>
      </div>
      <div class="row">
        <div class="mb-3 col-md-3">
          <label>Gender</label>
          <input type="text" class="form-control" name="gender" id="gender" value="<?php echo
$row['gender'];?>" readonly>
        </div>
        <div class="mb-3 col-md-3">
          <label>Location</label>
          <input type="text" class="form-control" name="location" id="location" value="<?php
echo $row['location'];?>" readonly>
        </div>
        <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
          <label>Birth Date</label>
          <input class="form-control" type="date" name="birthday" id="birthday" value="<?php
echo $row['birth_day'];?>" readonly>
        </div>
      </div>
      <div class="row">
        <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
          <label>Cell Number</label>

```

```

        <input type="text" class="form-control" maxlength="13" name="number" id="number"
value="<?php echo $row['cell_number']; ?>" readonly>
    </div>
    <?php if(($row['verif_status'])!=1){ ?>
    <div class="mb-3 col-md-3">
        <label>Cell Number not verified</label>                <?php
if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
        <input type="button" class="btn btn-primary"
onclick="document.location='sms/public/code.php?IDcode=<?php echo $row['id'];?>'"
value="Verify"><?php } ?>
    </div>
    <?php } ?>
</div>
<div class="row">
    <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
        <label>Role</label>
        <input type="text" class="form-control" maxlength="13" name="role" id="role"
value="<?php echo $row['role']; ?>" readonly>
    </div>
    <?php if(($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator' && $row['role']=='DRIVER'){?>
    <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
        <label>Plate Number</label>
        <input type="text" class="form-control" maxlength="13" name="plate_num"
id="plate_num" value="<?php echo $row['plate_num']; ?>" readonly>
    </div>
    <?php }?>
    </div>
    <input type="button" class="btn btn-primary" onclick="document.location='passenger-
details.php'" value="Back">
    <?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
    <input type="button" class="btn btn-primary"
onclick="document.location='edit.php?IDedit=<?php echo $row['id'];?>'" value="Edit">
    <button type="submit" class="btn btn-primary" name="delete_button">Delete</button>
    <input type="hidden" name="IDdelete" value="<?php echo $row['id'];?>">
    <?php } ?>
</form>

</div>
</div>

</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</main>

```

```

<footer class="footer">
<div class="container-fluid">
<div class="row text-muted">
<div class="col-8 text-start">
<ul class="list-inline">
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Support</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Privacy</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Terms of Service</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Contact</a>
</li>
</ul>
</div>
<div class="col-4 text-end">
<p class="mb-0">
&copy; 2022 - <a href="dashboard-default.html" class="text-muted">Spark</a>
</p>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>

```

```

<svg width="0" height="0" style="position:absolute">
<defs>
<symbol viewBox="0 0 512 512" id="ion-ios-pulse-strong">
<path
d="M448 273.001c-21.27 0-39.296 13.999-45.596 32.999h-38.857l-28.361-85.417a15.999 15.999 0
0 0-15.183-10.956c-.112 0-.224 0-.335.004a15.997 15.997 0 0 0-15.049 11.588l-44.484 155.262-
52.353-314.108C206.535 54.893 200.333 48 192 48s-13.693 5.776-15.525 13.135L115.496
306H16v31.999h112c7.348 0 13.75-5.003 15.525-12.134l45.368-182.177 51.324 307.94c1.229 7.377
7.397 11.92 14.864 12.344.308.018.614.028.919.028 7.097 0 13.406-3.701 15.381-10.594l49.744-
173.617 15.689 47.252A16.001 16.001 0 0 0 352 337.999h51.108C409.973 355.999 427.477 369 448
369c26.511 0 48-22.492 48-49 0-26.509-21.489-46.999-48-46.999z">
</path>
</symbol>
</defs>
</svg>
<script src="js/app.js"></script>

</body>

</html>

```

edit.php

```

<?php

include_once("connections/connections.php");
$con = connection();

if(!isset($_SESSION)){
    session_start();
}

if(!isset($_SESSION['UserLogin'])){
    echo header("Location: index.php");
}else{

if(!isset($_SESSION['Access']) && $_SESSION['Access'] == "administrator"){
    echo header("Location: index.php");
}

$idedit=$_GET['IDedit'];
$sql = "SELECT * FROM jeepq_list WHERE id = '$idedit'";
$students = $con->query($sql) or die($con->error);
$row = $students->fetch_assoc(); // retrieves 1 only (need loop statements)

if(isset($_POST['update_input'])){

    $fname = strtoupper($_POST['firstname']);
    $lname = strtoupper($_POST['lastname']);
    $birthday = $_POST['birthday'];
    $gender = strtoupper($_POST['gender']);
    $location = strtoupper($_POST['location']);
    $plate_num= strtoupper($_POST['plate_num']);
    $role=strtoupper($_POST['role']);
    $number = $_POST['number'];
    $verif_num = $_POST['verif_num'];

    $sql = "UPDATE jeepq_list SET first_name='$fname', last_name='$lname', gender='$gender',
    birth_day='$birthday', location='$location', cell_number='$number', verif_status='$verif_num',
    plate_num='$plate_num', role='$role' WHERE id='$idedit'";
    $con->query($sql) or die($con->error);

    echo header("Location: details.php?IDview=".$idedit); //redirects page to avoid double entry
}
}
?>
<?php include "header.php";?>

</nav>

```

```

<main class="content">
<div class="container-fluid">

<div class="header">
<h1 class="header-title">
Edit Passenger Details
</h1>
<nav aria-label="breadcrumb">
<ol class="breadcrumb">
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Home</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Accounts</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="passenger-details.php">Subscribers</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item active" aria-current="page">Edit Subscriber Details</li>
</ol>
</nav>
</div>

<div class="card">
<div class="card-header">

<h5 class="card-title mb-0">Private info</h5>
</div>
<div class="card-body">
    <form action="" method="post">

        <?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
        <div class="row">
            <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
                <label>First name</label>
                <input type="text" class="form-control" name="firstname" id="firstname"
value="<?php echo $row['first_name'];?>">
            </div>
            <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
                <label>Last name</label>
                <input type="text" class="form-control" name="lastname" id="lastname"
value="<?php echo $row['last_name'];?>">
            </div>
        </div>
        <div class="row">
            <div class="mb-3 col-md-3">
                <label>Gender</label>
                <select class="form-select flex-grow-1" name="gender" id="select">
                    <option value="MALE" <?php echo ($row['gender']=='MALE')?
'selected':";?>>MALE</option>
                    <option value="FEMALE" <?php echo ($row['gender']=='FEMALE')?
'selected':";?>>FEMALE</option>
                </select>
            </div>
        </div>
    </form>

```

```

        <div class="mb-3 col-md-3">
            <label>Location</label>
            <select class="form-select flex-grow-1" name="location" id="select">
                <option value="BAGUIO" <?php echo ($row['location']=='BAGUIO')?
'selected':";?>>BAGUIO</option>
                <option value="TRINIDAD" <?php echo ($row['location']=='TRINIDAD')?
'selected':";?>>TRINIDAD</option>
            </select>
        </div>
        <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
            <label>Birth Date</label>
            <input class="form-control" type="date" name="birthday" id="birthday"
value="<?php echo $row['birth_day'];?>"
            </div>
        </div>
        <div class="row">
            <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
                <label>Cell Number</label>
                <input type="text" class="form-control" maxlength="13" name="number"
id="number" value="<?php echo $row['cell_number']; ?>"
            </div>
            <?php if(($row['cell_number']!=1){; ?>
            <div class="mb-3 col-md-3">
                <label>Cell Number not verified</label>
                <input type="text" class="form-control" maxlength="1" name="verif_num"
id="verif_num" value="<?php echo $row['verif_status'];?>"
            </div>
            <?php } ?>
        </div>
        <div class="row">
            <div class="mb-3 col-md-3">
                <label>Role</label>
                <select onchange="yesnoCheck(this);" class="form-select flex-grow-1" name="role"
id="select">
                    <option value="PASSENGER" <?php echo ($row['role']=='PASSENGER')?
'selected':";?>>PASSENGER</option>
                    <option value="DRIVER" <?php echo ($row['role']=='DRIVER')?
'selected':";?>>DRIVER</option>
                </select>
            </div>
            <?php if(($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator' && $row['role']=='DRIVER'){?>
            <div class="mb-3 col-md-3">
                <label for="car">Plate Number</label>
                <input type="text" class="form-control" id="plate_num" name="plate_num"
value="<?php echo $row['plate_num'];?>" /><br />
            </div>
            <?php }?>
        </div>
        <input type="button" class="btn btn-primary"
onclick="document.location='details.php?IDview=<?php echo $row['id'];?>' value="Back">
        <?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>

```



```

<defs>
<symbol viewBox="0 0 512 512" id="ion-ios-pulse-strong">
<path
d="M448 273.001c-21.27 0-39.296 13.999-45.596 32.999h-38.857l-28.361-85.417a15.999 15.999 0
0 0-15.183-10.956c-.112 0-.224 0-.335.004a15.997 15.997 0 0 0-15.049 11.588l-44.484 155.262-
52.353-314.108C206.535 54.893 200.333 48 192 48s-13.693 5.776-15.525 13.135L115.496
306H16v31.999h112c7.348 0 13.75-5.003 15.525-12.134l45.368-182.177 51.324 307.94c1.229 7.377
7.397 11.92 14.864 12.344.308.018.614.028.919.028 7.097 0 13.406-3.701 15.381-10.594l49.744-
173.617 15.689 47.252A16.001 16.001 0 0 0 352 337.999h51.108C409.973 355.999 427.477 369 448
369c26.511 0 48-22.492 48-49 0-26.509-21.489-46.999-48-46.999z">
</path>
</symbol>
</defs>
</svg>
<script src="js/app.js"></script>
<script type="text/javascript">
function yesnoCheck(that) {
  if (that.value == "DRIVER") {
    alert("Input your Jeepney's plate number.");
    document.getElementById("ifYes").style.display = "block";
  } else {
    document.getElementById("ifYes").style.display = "none";
  }
}
</script>
</body>

</html>

```

header.php

```

<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="en">

<head>
<meta charset="utf-8">
<meta http-equiv="X-UA-Compatible" content="IE=edge">
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1, shrink-to-fit=no">
<meta name="description" content="Modern, flexible and responsive Bootstrap 5 admin &
dashboard template">
<meta name="author" content="Bootlab">

<title>JeeqQ Tracking System</title>

<!-- PICK ONE OF THE STYLES BELOW -->
<!--<link href="css/modern.css" rel="stylesheet"> -->
<link href="css/classic.css" rel="stylesheet">
<!-- <link href="css/dark.css" rel="stylesheet"> -->
<!-- <link href="css/light.css" rel="stylesheet"> -->

</head>

```

```

<body>
<div class="splash active">
<div class="splash-icon"></div>
</div>

<div class="wrapper">
<nav id="sidebar" class="sidebar">
<a class="sidebar-brand" href="index.html">
JeepQ
</a>
<div class="sidebar-content">
<div class="sidebar-user">

<div class="fw-bold">Welcome <?php echo $_SESSION['UserLogin'] ?></div>
<small><?php echo $_SESSION['Access'] ?> access </small>
</div>

<ul class="sidebar-nav">
<li class="sidebar-header">
Main
</li>
<li class="sidebar-item">
<a class="sidebar-link" href="index.php">
<i class="align-middle me-2 fas fa-fw fa-home"></i> <span class="align-middle">Home</span>
</a>
</li>
        <?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
        <li class="sidebar-item">
<a data-bs-target="#dashboards" data-bs-toggle="collapse" class="sidebar-link collapsed">
<i class="align-middle me-2 fas fa-fw fa-envelope"></i> <span class="align-
middle">Messages</span>
        </a>
        <ul id="dashboards" class="sidebar-dropdown list-unstyled collapse " data-bs-
parent="#sidebar">
<li class="sidebar-item"><a class="sidebar-link" href="sms/public/index.php">Send SMS
Message</a></li>
</ul>
</li>
        <?php } ?>
<!-- <li class="sidebar-item">
<a class="sidebar-link" href="tables-bootstrap.html">
<i class="align-middle me-2 fas fa-fw fa-chart-line"></i> <span class="align-
middle">Dashboard</span>
</a>
</li> -->
<li class="sidebar-item">
<a data-bs-target="#dashboards" data-bs-toggle="collapse" class="sidebar-link collapsed">
<i class="align-middle me-2 fas fa-fw fa-user-friends"></i> <span class="align-
middle">Accounts</span>

```

```

</a>
<ul id="dashboards" class="sidebar-dropdown list-unstyled collapse " data-bs-parent="#sidebar">
<?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
<li class="sidebar-item"><a class="sidebar-link" href="user-details.php">User Access</a></li>
<?php } ?>
<li class="sidebar-item"><a class="sidebar-link" href="passenger-details.php">Subscribers</a></li>
<li class="sidebar-item"><a class="sidebar-link" href="route-details.php">Routes</a></li>
</ul>
</li>
<!-- <li class="sidebar-item">
<a class="sidebar-link" href="tables-bootstrap.html">
<i class="align-middle me-2 fas fa-fw fa-cog"></i> <span class="align-middle">Settings</span>
</a>
</li> -->
<li class="sidebar-item">
<a class="sidebar-link" href="logout.php">
<i class="align-middle me-2 fas fa-fw fa-sign-out-alt"></i> <span class="align-
middle">Logout</span>
</a>
</li>
</ul>
</div>
</nav>

```

```

<div class="main">
<nav class="navbar navbar-expand navbar-theme">
<a class="sidebar-toggle d-flex me-2">
<i class="hamburger align-self-center"></i>
</a>

```

index.php

```

<?php
//checks if the session already set
if(!isset($_SESSION)){
    session_start();
}

if(!isset($_SESSION['UserLogin'])){
    echo header("Location: login.php");
}

include_once("connections/connections.php"); //para hnd paulit ulit na include
$con = connection(); //requesting connection to database

```

```

$sql = "SELECT * FROM jeepq_list ORDER BY id DESC";
$students = $con->query($sql) or die($con->error);
$row = $students->fetch_assoc(); // retrieves 1 only (need loop statements)
//print_r($row); //built in print array
// do{ //retrieves all $students->fetch_assoc() data
//   echo $row['first_name']." ".$row['last_name']."<br/>";
// }while($row = $students->fetch_assoc()); //execute code while statement is still true
//! + tab

```

```

//echo $_SESSION['access_token'];
//echo $_SESSION['subscriber_number'];

```

```
?>
```

```
<?php include "header.php";?>
```

```
</nav>
```

```
<main class="content">
```

```
<div class="container-fluid">
```

```
<div class="header">
```

```
<h1 class="header-title">
```

```
JeepQ Tracking System
```

```
</h1>
```

```
<nav aria-label="breadcrumb">
```

```
<ol class="breadcrumb">
```

```
<li class="breadcrumb-item active" aria-current="page">Introduction</li>
```

```
</ol>
```

```
</nav>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="row">
```

```
<div class="col-12">
```

```
<div class="card">
```

```
<div class="card-header">
```

```

<h5 class="card-title mb-0">Different areas in the Philippines, esp. In the Provinces, have trouble in
waiting for Jeepneys. This is because, most of the time, Jeepneys are already full when they pass by
some areas., queuing for Jeepneys is a huge problem on most areas. There's currently no system
available to help our Jeepney Service providers for data gathering to understand which areas and
what time do passengers need their services. <br> <br>

```

The goal of this project is to provide an effective data gathering system to capture data needed both by Jeepney drivers and passengers to provide real time view of the demand and available supply of Jeepney transportation services across different areas. Both passengers and drivers can use SMS to upload and view queuing information from the system.

An example of such are the Uber/Grab/Ankas/Trainsity services that were known to be very effective in booking, tracking, reserving transportation services using Cabs, Private Cars, Motorcycles, Trains etc. However, not all individuals afford to use these services as these transportation means are very expensive. And not all individuals have smartphones and internet to install and book such apps. The known public transportation in the Philippines are Jeepneys and yet, very little service providers resolve issues on Jeepney queuing. However, a very large percentage in the population

have cellphones and SMS load and this is something we can take advantage of as it can be used for a better data gathering system. </h5>

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="card-body">
```

```
<div class="my-5">&nbsp;  </div>
```

```
</main>
```

```
<svg width="0" height="0" style="position:absolute">
```

```
<defs>
```

```
<symbol viewBox="0 0 512 512" id="ion-ios-pulse-strong">
```

```
<path
```

```
d="M448 273.001c-21.27 0-39.296 13.999-45.596 32.999h-38.857l-28.361-85.417a15.999 15.999 0
```

```
0 0-15.183-10.956c-.112 0-.224 0-.335.004a15.997 15.997 0 0 0-15.049 11.588l-44.484 155.262-
```

```
52.353-314.108C206.535 54.893 200.333 48 192 48s-13.693 5.776-15.525 13.135L115.496
```

```
306H16v31.999h112c7.348 0 13.75-5.003 15.525-12.134l45.368-182.177 51.324 307.94c1.229 7.377
```

```
7.397 11.92 14.864 12.344.308.018.614.028.919.028 7.097 0 13.406-3.701 15.381-10.594l49.744-
```

```
173.617 15.689 47.252A16.001 16.001 0 0 0 352 337.999h51.108C409.973 355.999 427.477 369 448
```

```
369c26.511 0 48-22.492 48-49 0-26.509-21.489-46.999-48-46.999z">
```

```
</path>
```

```
</symbol>
```

```
</defs>
```

```
</svg>
```

```
<script src="js/app.js"></script>
```

```
<script src="https://cdnjs.cloudflare.com/ajax/libs/highlight.js/9.12.0/highlight.min.js"></script>
```

```
<script>
```

```
document.addEventListener("DOMContentLoaded", function() {
```

```
  $("pre code").each(function(i, block) {
```

```
    hljs.highlightBlock(block);
```

```
  });
```

```
});
```

```
</script>
```

```
</body>
```

```
</html>
```

login.php

```
<?php
```

```
if(!isset($_SESSION)){
```

```
    session_start();
```

```
}
```

```

include_once("connections/connections.php"); //para hnd paulit ulit na include
$con = connection();

if(isset($_POST['login'])){

    $username = $_POST['usernamepost'];
    $password = $_POST['passwordpost'];

    $sql = "SELECT * FROM jeepq_users WHERE username = '$username' AND password
=$password";
    $user = $con->query($sql) or die($con->error);
    $row = $user->fetch_assoc();
    $total = $user->num_rows;

    if($total > 0) {
        $_SESSION['UserLogin'] = $row['username'];
        $_SESSION['Access'] = $row['access'];
        echo header("Location: index.php");
    }else{
        echo "No User Found.";
    }
}

?>

<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="en">

<head>
<meta charset="utf-8">
<meta http-equiv="X-UA-Compatible" content="IE=edge">
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1, shrink-to-fit=no">
<meta name="description" content="Modern, flexible and responsive Bootstrap 5 admin &
dashboard template">
<meta name="author" content="Bootlab">

<title>JeeqQ Tracking System</title>

<!-- PICK ONE OF THE STYLES BELOW -->
<!-- <link href="css/modern.css" rel="stylesheet"> -->
<link href="css/classic.css" rel="stylesheet">
<!-- <link href="css/dark.css" rel="stylesheet"> -->
<!-- <link href="css/light.css" rel="stylesheet"> -->

</head>
<!-- SET YOUR THEME -->

<body class="theme-blue">

```

```

<div class="splash active">
<div class="splash-icon"></div>
</div>

<main class="main h-100 w-100">
<div class="container h-100">
<div class="row h-100">
<div class="col-sm-10 col-md-8 col-lg-6 mx-auto d-table h-100">
<div class="d-table-cell align-middle">

<div class="text-center mt-4">
<h1 class="h2">JeeqQ Tracking System</h1>
<p class="lead">
Your ride is ready!
</p>
</div>

<div class="card">
<div class="card-body">
<div class="m-sm-4">
<div class="text-center">

</div>
<form action="" method="post">
<div class="mb-3">
<label>Username</label>
<input class="form-control form-control-lg" type="text" name="usernamepost" id="usernamepost"
placeholder="Enter your username" />
</div>
<div class="mb-3">
<label>Password</label>
<input class="form-control form-control-lg" type="password" name="passwordpost"
id="passwordpost" placeholder="Enter your password" />
</div>
<div class="text-center mt-3">
<button class="btn btn-lg btn-primary" type="submit" name="login">Login</button>
<!-- <button type="submit" class="btn btn-lg btn-primary">Sign in</button> -->
</div>
</form>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</main>

<svg width="0" height="0" style="position:absolute">

```

```

<defs>
<symbol viewBox="0 0 512 512" id="ion-ios-pulse-strong">
<path
d="M448 273.001c-21.27 0-39.296 13.999-45.596 32.999h-38.857l-28.361-85.417a15.999 15.999 0
0 0-15.183-10.956c-.112 0-.224 0-.335.004a15.997 15.997 0 0 0-15.049 11.588l-44.484 155.262-
52.353-314.108C206.535 54.893 200.333 48 192 48s-13.693 5.776-15.525 13.135L115.496
306H16v31.999h112c7.348 0 13.75-5.003 15.525-12.134l45.368-182.177 51.324 307.94c1.229 7.377
7.397 11.92 14.864 12.344.308.018.614.028.919.028 7.097 0 13.406-3.701 15.381-10.594l49.744-
173.617 15.689 47.252A16.001 16.001 0 0 0 352 337.999h51.108C409.973 355.999 427.477 369 448
369c26.511 0 48-22.492 48-49 0-26.509-21.489-46.999-48-46.999z">
</path>
</symbol>
</defs>
</svg>
<script src="js/app.js"></script>

</body>
</html>

```

logout.php

```

<?php

session_start();
unset($_SESSION['UserLogin']);
unset($_SESSION['Access']);
echo header("Location: login.php");

```

passenger-details.php

```

<?php
//checks if the session already set
if(!isset($_SESSION)){
    session_start();
}

if(!isset($_SESSION['UserLogin'])){
    echo header("Location: login.php");
}

include_once("connections/connections.php"); //para hnd paulit ulit na include
$con = connection(); //requesting connection to database

$sql = "SELECT * FROM jeepq_list ORDER BY id DESC";
$students = $con->query($sql) or die($con->error);
$row = $students->fetch_assoc(); // retrieves 1 only (need loop stateents)
//print_r($row); //built in print array
// do{ //retrieves all $students->fetch_assoc() data
//     echo $row['first_name']. " ".$row['last_name']."<br/>";

```

```

// }while($row = $students->fetch_assoc()); //execute code while statement is still true
//! + tab

?>

<?php include "header.php";?>

</nav>
<main class="content">
<div class="container-fluid">

<div class="header">
<h1 class="header-title">
Subscribers
</h1>
<nav aria-label="breadcrumb">
<ol class="breadcrumb">
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Home</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="#">Accounts</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item active" aria-current="page">Subscribers</li>
</ol>
</nav>
</div>
<div class="row">
<div class="col-12">
<div class="card">
<div class="card-header">
<h5 class="card-title">Subscriber List</h5>
<h6 class="card-subtitle text-muted">
<?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
<button class="btn btn-primary" onclick="document.location='add.php'">Add</button> - Register
new passenger information.
<?php } ?>
</h6>
</div>
<div class="card-body">
<table id="datatables-reponsive" class="table table-striped" style="width:100%">
<thead>
<tr>
<th>First Name</th>
<th>Last Name</th>
<th>Gender</th>
<th>Location</th>
<th>Role</th>
<th>Status</th>
<th>Actions</th>
</tr>
</thead>
<tbody>

```

```

<?php do{ ?>
<tr>
<td><?php echo $row['first_name'];?></td>
<td><?php echo $row['last_name'];?></td>
<td><?php echo $row['gender'];?></td>
<td><?php echo $row['location'];?></td>
<td><?php echo $row['role'];?></td>
<td><?php if($row['verif_status']==1){ ?>
<span class="badge bg-success">Verified</span>
<?php }else{?>
<span class="badge bg-danger">Unverified</span></td>
<?php }?>
<td>
<a href="details.php?IDview=<?php echo $row['id'];?>"><i class="align-middle fas fa-fw fa-eye"></i></a>
  <?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
<a href="edit.php?IDedit=<?php echo $row['id'];?>"><i class="align-middle fas fa-fw fa-pen"></i></a>
<a href="details.php?IDview=<?php echo $row['id'];?>"><i class="align-middle fas fa-fw fa-trash"></i></a></td>
<?php } ?>
</tr>
<?php }while($row = $students->fetch_assoc()) ?>
</tbody>
</table>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</main>
<footer class="footer">
<div class="container-fluid">
<div class="row text-muted">
<div class="col-8 text-start">
<ul class="list-inline">
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Support</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Privacy</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Terms of Service</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Contact</a>
</li>
</ul>
</div>

```

```

<div class="col-4 text-end">
<p class="mb-0">
&copy; 2022 - <a href="dashboard-default.html" class="text-muted">Spark</a>
</p>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>

```

```

<svg width="0" height="0" style="position:absolute">
<defs>
<symbol viewBox="0 0 512 512" id="ion-ios-pulse-strong">
<path
d="M448 273.001c-21.27 0-39.296 13.999-45.596 32.999h-38.857l-28.361-85.417a15.999 15.999 0
0 0-15.183-10.956c-.112 0-.224 0-.335.004a15.997 15.997 0 0 0-15.049 11.588l-44.484 155.262-
52.353-314.108C206.535 54.893 200.333 48 192 48s-13.693 5.776-15.525 13.135L115.496
306H16v31.999h112c7.348 0 13.75-5.003 15.525-12.134l45.368-182.177 51.324 307.94c1.229 7.377
7.397 11.92 14.864 12.344.308.018.614.028.919.028 7.097 0 13.406-3.701 15.381-10.594l49.744-
173.617 15.689 47.252A16.001 16.001 0 0 0 352 337.999h51.108C409.973 355.999 427.477 369 448
369c26.511 0 48-22.492 48-49 0-26.509-21.489-46.999-48-46.999z">
</path>
</symbol>
</defs>
</svg>
<script src="js/app.js"></script>

```

```

<script>
document.addEventListener("DOMContentLoaded", function() {
// Datatables Responsive
$("#datatables-reponsive").DataTable({
responsive: true
});
});
</script>
</body>

```

```
</html>
```

route-add.php

```

<?php

include_once("connections/connections.php");
$con = connection();

if(!isset($_SESSION)){
    session_start();
}
if(!isset($_SESSION['UserLogin'])){

```

```

    echo header("Location: index.php");
}else{

    $sql = "SELECT DISTINCT code FROM routes ORDER BY code ASC";
    $routes = $con->query($sql) or die($con->error);
    $row = $routes->fetch_assoc(); // retrieves 1 only (need loop statements)

if(isset($_POST['submit_input'])){

    $codeselect = strtoupper($_POST['codeselect']);
    echo header("Location: route-add-next.php?codeedit=$codeselect");
}
}

?>

<?php include "header.php";?>

</nav>
<main class="content">
<div class="container-fluid">

<div class="header">
<h1 class="header-title">
Add New Subscribers
</h1>
<nav aria-label="breadcrumb">
<ol class="breadcrumb">
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Home</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Accounts</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="passenger-details.php">Passenger List</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item active" aria-current="page">Add New Subscribers</li>
</ol>
</nav>
</div>

<div class="card">
<div class="card-header">
<h5 class="card-title mb-0">Private info</h5>
</div>
<div class="card-body">
<form action="" method="post">
    <?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
    <div class="row">
        <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">

```

```

        <label>Access</label>
        <select class="form-select flex-grow-1" name="codeselect" id="select">
<option value="">Select...</option>
<?php do{ ?>
<option value=""<?php echo ($row['code'])?>"><?php echo ($row['code'])?></option>
<?php }while($row = $routes->fetch_assoc()) ?>
</select>
    </div>
</div>
    <input type="button" class="btn btn-primary" onclick="document.location='route-
details.php'" value="Back">
    <?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
    <button type="submit" class="btn btn-primary" name="submit_input" value="Submit
Form">Next</button>
    <?php } ?>
    <?php }else{?>
    <h6 class="card-title mb-0">You are not allowed to access this page. </h6><br>
    <input type="button" class="btn btn-primary"
onclick="document.location='index.php'" value="Home">
    <?php } ?>
    </form>
</div>
</div>
    </div>
</main>

<footer class="footer">
<div class="container-fluid">
<div class="row text-muted">
<div class="col-8 text-start">
<ul class="list-inline">
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Support</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Privacy</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Terms of Service</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Contact</a>
</li>
</ul>
</div>
<div class="col-4 text-end">
<p class="mb-0">
&copy; 2022 - <a href="dashboard-default.html" class="text-muted">Spark</a>
</p>
</div>
</div>

```

```

</div>
</footer>
</div>
</div>

<svg width="0" height="0" style="position:absolute">
<defs>
<symbol viewBox="0 0 512 512" id="ion-ios-pulse-strong">
<path
d="M448 273.001c-21.27 0-39.296 13.999-45.596 32.999h-38.857l-28.361-85.417a15.999 15.999 0
0 0-15.183-10.956c-.112 0-.224 0-.335.004a15.997 15.997 0 0 0-15.049 11.588l-44.484 155.262-
52.353-314.108C206.535 54.893 200.333 48 192 48s-13.693 5.776-15.525 13.135L115.496
306H16v31.999h112c7.348 0 13.75-5.003 15.525-12.134l45.368-182.177 51.324 307.94c1.229 7.377
7.397 11.92 14.864 12.344.308.018.614.028.919.028 7.097 0 13.406-3.701 15.381-10.594l49.744-
173.617 15.689 47.252A16.001 16.001 0 0 0 352 337.999h51.108C409.973 355.999 427.477 369 448
369c26.511 0 48-22.492 48-49 0-26.509-21.489-46.999-48-46.999z">
</path>
</symbol>
</defs>
</svg>
<script src="js/app.js"></script>

</body>

</html>

```

route-add-next.php

```

<?php

include_once("connections/connections.php");
$con = connection();

if(!isset($_SESSION)){
    session_start();
}
if(!isset($_SESSION['UserLogin'])){
    echo header("Location: index.php");
}else{

    $codeedit=$_GET['codeedit'];

    $sql = "SELECT * FROM routes WHERE code = '$codeedit'";
    $routes = $con->query($sql) or die($con->error);
    $row = $routes->fetch_assoc(); // retrieves 1 only (need loop stateents)

if(isset($_POST['submit_input'])){

    $state = $row['state'];
    $city = $row['city'];

```

```

$zipcode = $row['zipcode'];
$barangay = $row['barangay'];
$route_name = $row['route-name'];
$sequence = $_POST['sequence'];
$puj_stops = $_POST['puj_stop'];

$sql = "INSERT INTO `routes`(`state`, `city`, `zipcode`, `barangay`, `route-name`, `sequence`, `puj-
stops`, `code`) VALUES
('$state', '$city', '$zipcode', '$barangay', '$route_name', '$sequence', '$puj_stops', '$codeedit')";
$con->query($sql) or die($con->error);
echo header("Location: route-details.php"); //redirects page to avoid double entry uploads
}
}

```

```
?>
```

```
<?php include "header.php";?>
```

```
</nav>
```

```
<main class="content">
```

```
<div class="container-fluid">
```

```
<div class="header">
```

```
<h1 class="header-title">
```

```
Add New Subscribers
```

```
</h1>
```

```
<nav aria-label="breadcrumb">
```

```
<ol class="breadcrumb">
```

```
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Home</a></li>
```

```
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Accounts</a></li>
```

```
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="passenger-details.php">Passenger List</a></li>
```

```
<li class="breadcrumb-item active" aria-current="page">Add New Subscribers</li>
```

```
</ol>
```

```
</nav>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="card">
```

```
<div class="card-header">
```

```
<h5 class="card-title mb-0">Private info : <?php echo $codeedit;?></h5>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="card-body">
```

```
<form action="" method="post">
```

```
<?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
```

```
<div class="row">
```

```

        <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
            <label>State</label>
            <input type="text" class="form-control" name="state" id="state" value="<?php echo
$row['state'];?>" readonly>
        </div>
        <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
            <label>City</label>
            <input type="text" class="form-control" name="city" id="city" value="<?php echo
$row['city'];?>" readonly>
        </div>
    </div>
    <div class="row">
        <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
            <label>Zip Code</label>
            <input type="text" class="form-control" name="zipcode" id="zipcode" value="<?php echo
$row['zipcode'];?>" readonly>
        </div>
        <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
            <label>Barangay</label>
            <input type="text" class="form-control" name="barangay" id="barangay" value="<?php
echo $row['barangay'];?>" readonly>
        </div>
    </div>
    <div class="row">
        <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
            <label>Route Name</label>
            <input type="text" class="form-control" name="route-name" id="route-name"
value="<?php echo $row['route-name'];?>" readonly>
        </div>
        <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
            <label>Route Code</label>
            <input type="text" class="form-control" name="code" id="code" value="<?php echo
$row['code'];?>" readonly>
        </div>
    </div>
    <div class="row">
        <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
            <label>Jeepney Stops</label>
            <select multiple class="form-control">
                <?php do{ ?>
<option><?php echo $row['sequence'];?> - <?php echo $row['puj-stops'];?></option>
<?php }while($row = $routes->fetch_assoc()) ?>
            </select>
        </div>
    </div>
    <div class="row">
        <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
            <label>Sequence</label>
            <input type="text" class="form-control" name="sequence" id="sequence">
        </div>
        <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">

```



```

<svg width="0" height="0" style="position:absolute">
<defs>
<symbol viewBox="0 0 512 512" id="ion-ios-pulse-strong">
<path
d="M448 273.001c-21.27 0-39.296 13.999-45.596 32.999h-38.857l-28.361-85.417a15.999 15.999 0
0 0-15.183-10.956c-.112 0-.224 0-.335.004a15.997 15.997 0 0 0-15.049 11.588l-44.484 155.262-
52.353-314.108C206.535 54.893 200.333 48 192 48s-13.693 5.776-15.525 13.135L115.496
306H16v31.999h112c7.348 0 13.75-5.003 15.525-12.134l45.368-182.177 51.324 307.94c1.229 7.377
7.397 11.92 14.864 12.344.308.018.614.028.919.028 7.097 0 13.406-3.701 15.381-10.594l49.744-
173.617 15.689 47.252A16.001 16.001 0 0 0 352 337.999h51.108C409.973 355.999 427.477 369 448
369c26.511 0 48-22.492 48-49 0-26.509-21.489-46.999-48-46.999z">
</path>
</symbol>
</defs>
</svg>
<script src="js/app.js"></script>

</body>

</html>

```

route-delete.php

```

<?php
include_once("connections/connections.php");
$con = connection();

//echo $_POST['IDdelete'];
//print_r($_POST);

if(!isset($_SESSION)){
    session_start();
}

if(!isset($_SESSION['UserLogin'])){
    echo header("Location: index.php");
}else{

if(isset($_POST['delete_button3'])){

    $iddelete = $_POST['delete3'];
    $sql = "DELETE FROM routes WHERE id ='$iddelete";
    $con->query($sql) or die ($con->error);

    echo header("Location: route-details.php");
}
}
?>

```

route-delete-new.php

```

<?php

include_once("connections/connections.php");
$con = connection();

if(!isset($_SESSION)){
    session_start();
}
if(!isset($_SESSION['UserLogin'])){
    echo header("Location: index.php");
}else{

    $iddelete=$_GET['iddelete'];

    $sql = "SELECT * FROM routes WHERE id = '$iddelete'";
    $routes = $con->query($sql) or die($con->error);
    $row = $routes->fetch_assoc(); // retrieves 1 only (need loop statements)

if(isset($_POST['submit_input'])){

    $state = $_POST['state'];
    $city = $_POST['city'];
    $zipcode = $_POST['zipcode'];
    $barangay = $_POST['barangay'];
    $route_name = $_POST['route-name'];
    $code = $_POST['code'];
    $sequence = $_POST['sequence'];
    $puj_stops = $_POST['puj_stop'];

    $sql1 = "UPDATE routes SET state='$state', city='$city', zipcode='$zipcode', barangay='$barangay',
`route-name`='$route_name', sequence='$sequence', `puj-stops`='$puj_stops', code='$code',
id='$idedit' WHERE id='$idedit'";
    $con->query($sql1) or die($con->error);
    echo header("Location: route-details.php"); //redirects page to avoid double entry uploads
}
}

?>

<?php include "header.php";?>

</nav>
<main class="content">
<div class="container-fluid">

```

```

<div class="header">
<h1 class="header-title">
Edit Routes
</h1>
<nav aria-label="breadcrumb">
<ol class="breadcrumb">
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Home</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Accounts</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="passenger-details.php">Routes</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item active" aria-current="page">Edit Routes</li>
</ol>
</nav>
</div>

```

```

<div class="card">
<div class="card-header">
<h5 class="card-title mb-0">Private info : <?php echo $codeedit;?></h5>
</div>
<div class="card-body">
<form action="route-delete.php" method="post">
<?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
<div class="row">
<div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
<label>State</label>
<input type="text" class="form-control" name="state" id="state" value="<?php echo
$row['state'];?>" readonly>
</div>
<div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
<label>City</label>
<input type="text" class="form-control" name="city" id="city" value="<?php echo
$row['city'];?>" readonly>
</div>
</div>
<div class="row">
<div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
<label>Zip Code</label>
<input type="text" class="form-control" name="zipcode" id="zipcode" value="<?php echo
$row['zipcode'];?>" readonly>
</div>
<div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
<label>Barangay</label>
<input type="text" class="form-control" name="barangay" id="barangay" value="<?php
echo $row['barangay'];?>" readonly>
</div>
</div>
<div class="row">
<div class="mb-3 col-md-6">

```

```

        <label>Route Name</label>
        <input type="text" class="form-control" name="route-name" id="route-name"
value="<?php echo $row['route-name'];?>" readonly>
    </div>
    <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
        <label>Route Code</label>
        <input type="text" class="form-control" name="code" id="code" value="<?php echo
$row['code'];?>" readonly>
    </div>
</div>

<div class="row">
    <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
        <label>Sequence</label>
        <input type="text" class="form-control" name="sequence" id="sequence" value="<?php
echo $row['sequence'];?>" readonly>
    </div>
    <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
        <label>Route Stop</label>
        <input type="text" class="form-control" name="puj_stop" id="puj_stop" value="<?php
echo $row['puj-stops'];?>" readonly>
    </div>
</div>
<input type="button" class="btn btn-primary" onclick="document.location='route-
details.php'" value="Back">
<?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
<button type="submit" class="btn btn-primary" name="delete_button3">Delete</button>
<input type="hidden" name="delete3" value="<?php echo $row['id'];?>">
    <?php } ?>
    <?php }else{?>
        <h6 class="card-title mb-0">You are not allowed to access this page. </h6><br>
        <input type="button" class="btn btn-primary"
onclick="document.location='index.php'" value="Home">
    <?php } ?>
</form>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</main>

<footer class="footer">
<div class="container-fluid">
<div class="row text-muted">
<div class="col-8 text-start">
<ul class="list-inline">
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Support</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Privacy</a>
</li>

```

```

<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Terms of Service</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Contact</a>
</li>
</ul>
</div>
<div class="col-4 text-end">
<p class="mb-0">
&copy; 2022 - <a href="dashboard-default.html" class="text-muted">Spark</a>
</p>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>

```

```

<svg width="0" height="0" style="position:absolute">
<defs>
<symbol viewBox="0 0 512 512" id="ion-ios-pulse-strong">
<path
d="M448 273.001c-21.27 0-39.296 13.999-45.596 32.999h-38.857l-28.361-85.417a15.999 15.999 0
0 0-15.183-10.956c-.112 0-.224 0-.335.004a15.997 15.997 0 0 0-15.049 11.588l-44.484 155.262-
52.353-314.108C206.535 54.893 200.333 48 192 48s-13.693 5.776-15.525 13.135L115.496
306H16v31.999h112c7.348 0 13.75-5.003 15.525-12.134l45.368-182.177 51.324 307.94c1.229 7.377
7.397 11.92 14.864 12.344.308.018.614.028.919.028 7.097 0 13.406-3.701 15.381-10.594l49.744-
173.617 15.689 47.252A16.001 16.001 0 0 0 352 337.999h51.108C409.973 355.999 427.477 369 448
369c26.511 0 48-22.492 48-49 0-26.509-21.489-46.999-48-46.999z">
</path>
</symbol>
</defs>
</svg>
<script src="js/app.js"></script>

```

```
</body>
```

```
</html>
```

route-details.php

```

<?php
//checks if the session already set
if(!isset($_SESSION)){
    session_start();
}

```

```

if(!isset($_SESSION['UserLogin'])){

```

```

    echo header("Location: login.php");
}

include_once("connections/connections.php"); //para hnd paulit ulit na include
$con = connection(); //requesting connection to database

$sql = "SELECT DISTINCT state, city, zipcode, code, barangay FROM routes ORDER BY id DESC";
$routes = $con->query($sql) or die($con->error);
$row = $routes->fetch_assoc(); // retrieves 1 only (need loop statements)
//print_r($row); //built in print array
// do{ //retrieves all $routes->fetch_assoc() data
//   echo $row['first_name']." ".$row['last_name']."<br/>";
// }while($row = $routes->fetch_assoc()); //execute code while statement is still true
//! + tab

?>

<?php include "header.php";?>

</nav>
<main class="content">
<div class="container-fluid">

<div class="header">
<h1 class="header-title">
Routes
</h1>
<nav aria-label="breadcrumb">
<ol class="breadcrumb">
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Home</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="#">Accounts</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item active" aria-current="page">Routes</li>
</ol>
</nav>
</div>
<div class="row">

<div class="col-12">
<div class="card">
<div class="card-header">
<h5 class="card-title">Route List</h5>
<h6 class="card-subtitle text-muted">
<?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
<button class="btn btn-primary" onclick="document.location='route-add.php'">Add</button> -
Register new route information.
<?php } ?>
</h6>
</div>
<div class="card-body">

```

```

<table id="datatables-reponsive" class="table table-striped" style="width:100%">
<thead>
<tr>
<th>State</th>
<th>City</th>
<th>Zip Code</th>
<th>Barangay</th>
<th>Code</th>
<th>Actions</th>
</tr>
</thead>
<tbody>

<?php do{ ?>
<tr>
<td><?php echo $row['state'];?></td>
<td><?php echo $row['city'];?></td>
<td><?php echo $row['zipcode'];?></td>
<td><?php echo $row['barangay'];?></td>
<td><?php echo $row['code'];?></td>
<td>
<a href="route-details-view.php?codeview=<?php echo $row['code'];?>"><i class="align-middle fas fa-fw fa-eye"></i></a>
<?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
<a href="route-edit.php?codeedit=<?php echo $row['code'];?>"><i class="align-middle fas fa-fw fa-pen"></i></a></td>
<?php } ?></td>
</tr>
<?php }while($row = $routes->fetch_assoc()) ?>

</tbody>
</table>

</div>
</div>
</div>

</div>
</main>
<footer class="footer">
<div class="container-fluid">
<div class="row text-muted">
<div class="col-8 text-start">
<ul class="list-inline">
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Support</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Privacy</a>
</li>

```



```

<?php
//checks if the session already set
include_once("connections/connections.php"); //para hnd paulit ulit na include
$con = connection(); //requesting connection to database

if(!isset($_SESSION)){
    session_start();
}

if(!isset($_SESSION['UserLogin'])){
    echo header("Location: index.php");
}else{

$codeview = $_GET['codeview'];

$sql = "SELECT * FROM routes WHERE code = '$codeview' ORDER BY sequence + 0 ASC";
$routes = $con->query($sql) or die($con->error);
$row = $routes->fetch_assoc(); // retrieves 1 only (need loop statements)

}

?>

<?php include "header.php";?>

</nav>
<main class="content">
<div class="container-fluid">

<div class="header">
<h1 class="header-title">
Route Details
</h1>
<nav aria-label="breadcrumb">
<ol class="breadcrumb">
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Home</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Accounts</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="passenger-details.php">Routes</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item active" aria-current="page">Route Details</li>
</ol>
</nav>
</div>

<div class="card">
<div class="card-header">

```

```

    <h5 class="card-title mb-0">Private info</h5>
</div>
<div class="card-body">
    <form action="user-delete.php" method="post">
        <div class="row">
            <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
                <label>State</label>
                <input type="text" class="form-control" name="state" id="state" value="<?php echo
$rowse['state'];?>" readonly>
            </div>
            <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
                <label>City</label>
                <input type="text" class="form-control" name="city" id="city" value="<?php echo
$rowse['city'];?>" readonly>
            </div>
        </div>
        <div class="row">
            <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
                <label>Zip Code</label>
                <input type="text" class="form-control" name="zipcode" id="zipcode" value="<?php
echo $rowse['zipcode'];?>" readonly>
            </div>
            <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
                <label>Barangay</label>
                <input type="text" class="form-control" name="barangay" id="barangay" value="<?php
echo $rowse['barangay'];?>" readonly>
            </div>
        </div>
        <div class="row">
            <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
                <label>Route Name</label>
                <input type="text" class="form-control" name="route-name" id="route-name"
value="<?php echo $rowse['route-name'];?>" readonly>
            </div>
            <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
                <label>Route Code</label>
                <input type="text" class="form-control" name="code" id="code" value="<?php echo
$rowse['code'];?>" readonly>
            </div>
        </div>
        <div class="row">
            <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
                <label>Jeepney Stops</label>
                <select multiple class="form-control">
                    <?php do{ ?>
<option><?php echo $rowse['sequence'];?> - <?php echo $rowse['puj-stops'];?></option>
<?php }while($rowse = $routes->fetch_assoc()) ?>
                </select>
            </div>
        </div>
    </form>
</div>

```

```

        <input type="button" class="btn btn-primary" onclick="document.location='route-
details.php'" value="Back">
        <?php if($_SESSION['Access']== 'administrator'){?>
        <input type="button" class="btn btn-primary" onclick="document.location='route-
edit.php?codeedit=<?php echo $codeview;?>" value="Edit">
        <?php } ?>

```

```

    </form>

```

```

</div>

```

```

</main>

```

```

<footer class="footer">

```

```

<div class="container-fluid">

```

```

<div class="row text-muted">

```

```

<div class="col-8 text-start">

```

```

<ul class="list-inline">

```

```

<li class="list-inline-item">

```

```

<a class="text-muted" href="#">Support</a>

```

```

</li>

```

```

<li class="list-inline-item">

```

```

<a class="text-muted" href="#">Privacy</a>

```

```

</li>

```

```

<li class="list-inline-item">

```

```

<a class="text-muted" href="#">Terms of Service</a>

```

```

</li>

```

```

<li class="list-inline-item">

```

```

<a class="text-muted" href="#">Contact</a>

```

```

</li>

```

```

</ul>

```

```

</div>

```

```

<div class="col-4 text-end">

```

```

<p class="mb-0">

```

```

&copy; 2022 - <a href="dashboard-default.html" class="text-muted">Spark</a>

```

```

</p>

```

```

</div>

```

```

</div>

```

```

</div>

```

```

</footer>

```

```

</div>
</div>

<svg width="0" height="0" style="position:absolute">
<defs>
<symbol viewBox="0 0 512 512" id="ion-ios-pulse-strong">
<path
d="M448 273.001c-21.27 0-39.296 13.999-45.596 32.999h-38.857l-28.361-85.417a15.999 15.999 0
0 0-15.183-10.956c-.112 0-.224 0-.335.004a15.997 15.997 0 0 0-15.049 11.588l-44.484 155.262-
52.353-314.108C206.535 54.893 200.333 48 192 48s-13.693 5.776-15.525 13.135L115.496
306H16v31.999h112c7.348 0 13.75-5.003 15.525-12.134l45.368-182.177 51.324 307.94c1.229 7.377
7.397 11.92 14.864 12.344.308.018.614.028.919.028 7.097 0 13.406-3.701 15.381-10.594l49.744-
173.617 15.689 47.252A16.001 16.001 0 0 0 352 337.999h51.108C409.973 355.999 427.477 369 448
369c26.511 0 48-22.492 48-49 0-26.509-21.489-46.999-48-46.999z">
</path>
</symbol>
</defs>
</svg>
<script src="js/app.js"></script>

</body>

</html>

```

route-edit.php

```

<?php

include_once("connections/connections.php");
$con = connection();

if(!isset($_SESSION)){
    session_start();
}
if(!isset($_SESSION['UserLogin'])){
    echo header("Location: index.php");
}else{

    $codeedit=$_GET['codeedit'];

    $sql = "SELECT * FROM routes WHERE code = '$codeedit'";
    $routes = $con->query($sql) or die($con->error);
    $row = $routes->fetch_assoc(); // retrieves 1 only (need loop stateents)

if(isset($_POST['submit_input'])){

    $codeselect = strtoupper($_POST['puj_stop']);
    echo header("Location: route-add-next.php?codeedit=$codeselect");

}
}

```

```
?>
```

```
<?php include "header.php";?>
```

```
</nav>
```

```
<main class="content">
```

```
<div class="container-fluid">
```

```
<div class="header">
```

```
<h1 class="header-title">
```

```
Add New Subscribers
```

```
</h1>
```

```
<nav aria-label="breadcrumb">
```

```
<ol class="breadcrumb">
```

```
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Home</a></li>
```

```
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Accounts</a></li>
```

```
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="passenger-details.php">Passenger List</a></li>
```

```
<li class="breadcrumb-item active" aria-current="page">Add New Subscribers</li>
```

```
</ol>
```

```
</nav>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="card">
```

```
<div class="card-header">
```

```
<h5 class="card-title mb-0">Private info : <?php echo $codeedit;?></h5>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="card-body">
```

```
<form action="" method="post">
```

```
<?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
```

```
<div class="row">
```

```
<div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
```

```
<label>State</label>
```

```
<input type="text" class="form-control" name="state" id="state" value="<?php echo $row['state'];?>" readonly>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
```

```
<label>City</label>
```

```
<input type="text" class="form-control" name="city" id="city" value="<?php echo $row['city'];?>" readonly>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="row">
```

```
<div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
```

```
<label>Zip Code</label>
```

```

        <input type="text" class="form-control" name="zipcode" id="zipcode" value="<?php echo
$row['zipcode'];?>" readonly>
    </div>
    <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
        <label>Barangay</label>
        <input type="text" class="form-control" name="barangay" id="barangay" value="<?php
echo $row['barangay'];?>" readonly>
    </div>
</div>
<div class="row">
    <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
        <label>Route Name</label>
        <input type="text" class="form-control" name="route-name" id="route-name"
value="<?php echo $row['route-name'];?>" readonly>
    </div>
    <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
        <label>Route Code</label>
        <input type="text" class="form-control" name="code" id="code" value="<?php echo
$row['code'];?>" readonly>
    </div>
</div>

<div class="row">
    <table id="datatables-reponsive" class="table table-striped" style="width:100%">
<thead>
<tr>
<th>Code</th>
<th>Sequence</th>
<th>Route Stops</th>
<th>Actions</th>
</tr>
</thead>
<tbody>
<?php do{ ?>
<tr>
<td><?php echo $row['code'];?></td>
<td><?php echo $row['sequence'];?></td>
<td><?php echo $row['puj-stops'];?></td>
<td>
<a href="route-edit-new.php?idedit=<?php echo $row['id'];?>"><i class="align-middle fas fa-fw fa-
pen"></i></a>
<a href="route-delete-new.php?iddelete=<?php echo $row['id'];?>"><i class="align-middle fas fa-fw
fa-trash"></i></a></td>
</tr>
                <?php }while($row = $routes->fetch_assoc()) ?>
</tbody>
</table>

</div>
    <input type="button" class="btn btn-primary" onclick="document.location='route-
details.php'" value="Back">

```

```

    <?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
    <button type="submit" class="btn btn-primary" name="submit_input" value="Submit
Form">Update</button>
    <?php } ?>
    <?php }else{?>
    <h6 class="card-title mb-0">You are not allowed to access this page. </h6><br>
    <input type="button" class="btn btn-primary"
onclick="document.location='index.php'" value="Home">
    <?php } ?>
    </form>

```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</main>
```

```
<footer class="footer">
```

```
<div class="container-fluid">
```

```
<div class="row text-muted">
```

```
<div class="col-8 text-start">
```

```
<ul class="list-inline">
```

```
<li class="list-inline-item">
```

```
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Support</a>
```

```
</li>
```

```
<li class="list-inline-item">
```

```
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Privacy</a>
```

```
</li>
```

```
<li class="list-inline-item">
```

```
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Terms of Service</a>
```

```
</li>
```

```
<li class="list-inline-item">
```

```
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Contact</a>
```

```
</li>
```

```
</ul>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="col-4 text-end">
```

```
<p class="mb-0">
```

```
&copy; 2022 - <a href="dashboard-default.html" class="text-muted">Spark</a>
```

```
</p>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</footer>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<svg width="0" height="0" style="position:absolute">
```

```
<defs>
```

```
<symbol viewBox="0 0 512 512" id="ion-ios-pulse-strong">
```

```
<path
```

```
d="M448 273.001c-21.27 0-39.296 13.999-45.596 32.999h-38.857l-28.361-85.417a15.999 15.999 0
```

```
0 0-15.183-10.956c-.112 0-.224 0-.335.004a15.997 15.997 0 0 0-15.049 11.588l-44.484 155.262-
```

```

52.353-314.108C206.535 54.893 200.333 48 192 48s-13.693 5.776-15.525 13.135L115.496
306H16v31.999h112c7.348 0 13.75-5.003 15.525-12.134l45.368-182.177 51.324 307.94c1.229 7.377
7.397 11.92 14.864 12.344.308.018.614.028.919.028 7.097 0 13.406-3.701 15.381-10.594l49.744-
173.617 15.689 47.252A16.001 16.001 0 0 0 352 337.999h51.108C409.973 355.999 427.477 369 448
369c26.511 0 48-22.492 48-49 0-26.509-21.489-46.999-48-46.999z">
</path>
</symbol>
</defs>
</svg>
<script src="js/app.js"></script>

</body>

</html>

```

route-edit-new.php

```

<?php

include_once("connections/connections.php");
$con = connection();

if(!isset($_SESSION)){
    session_start();
}
if(!isset($_SESSION['UserLogin'])){
    echo header("Location: index.php");
}else{

    $idedit=$_GET['idedit'];

    $sql = "SELECT * FROM routes WHERE id = '$idedit'";
    $routes = $con->query($sql) or die($con->error);
    $row = $routes->fetch_assoc(); // retrieves 1 only (need loop stateents)

if(isset($_POST['submit_input'])){

    $state = $_POST['state'];
    $city = $_POST['city'];
    $zipcode = $_POST['zipcode'];
    $barangay = $_POST['barangay'];
    $route_name = $_POST['route-name'];
    $code = $_POST['code'];
    $sequence = $_POST['sequence'];
    $puj_stops = $_POST['puj_stop'];

    $sql1 = "UPDATE routes SET state='$state', city='$city', zipcode='$zipcode', barangay='$barangay',
`route-name`='$route_name', sequence='$sequence', `puj-stops`='$puj_stops', code='$code',
id='$idedit' WHERE id='$idedit'";

```

```

$con->query($sql1) or die($con->error);
echo header("Location: route-details.php"); //redirects page to avoid double entry uploads
}
}

?>

<?php include "header.php";?>

</nav>
<main class="content">
<div class="container-fluid">

<div class="header">
<h1 class="header-title">
Edit Routes
</h1>
<nav aria-label="breadcrumb">
<ol class="breadcrumb">
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Home</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Accounts</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="passenger-details.php">Routes</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item active" aria-current="page">Edit Routes</li>
</ol>
</nav>
</div>

<div class="card">
<div class="card-header">
<h5 class="card-title mb-0">Private info : <?php echo $codeedit;?></h5>
</div>
<div class="card-body">
<form action="" method="post">
<?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
<div class="row">
<div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
<label>State</label>
<input type="text" class="form-control" name="state" id="state" value="<?php echo
$row['state'];?>">
</div>
<div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
<label>City</label>
<input type="text" class="form-control" name="city" id="city" value="<?php echo
$row['city'];?>">
</div>

```

```

</div>
<div class="row">
  <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
    <label>Zip Code</label>
    <input type="text" class="form-control" name="zipcode" id="zipcode" value="<?php echo
$řrow['zipcode'];?>">
  </div>
  <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
    <label>Barangay</label>
    <input type="text" class="form-control" name="barangay" id="barangay" value="<?php
echo $řrow['barangay'];?>">
  </div>
</div>
<div class="row">
  <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
    <label>Route Name</label>
    <input type="text" class="form-control" name="route-name" id="route-name"
value="<?php echo $řrow['route-name'];?>">
  </div>
  <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
    <label>Route Code</label>
    <input type="text" class="form-control" name="code" id="code" value="<?php echo
$řrow['code'];?>">
  </div>
</div>

<div class="row">
  <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
    <label>Sequence</label>
    <input type="text" class="form-control" name="sequence" id="sequence" value="<?php
echo $řrow['sequence'];?>">
  </div>
  <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
    <label>Route Stop</label>
    <input type="text" class="form-control" name="puj_stop" id="puj_stop" value="<?php
echo $řrow['puj-stops'];?>">
  </div>
</div>
  <input type="button" class="btn btn-primary" onclick="document.location='route-
details.php'" value="Back">
  <?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
  <button type="submit" class="btn btn-primary" name="submit_input" value="Submit
Form">Update</button>
  <?php } ?>
  <?php }else{?>
  <h6 class="card-title mb-0">You are not allowed to access this page. </h6><br>
  <input type="button" class="btn btn-primary"
onclick="document.location='index.php'" value="Home">
  <?php } ?>
</form>
</div>

```

```

</div>
  </div>
</main>

<footer class="footer">
<div class="container-fluid">
<div class="row text-muted">
<div class="col-8 text-start">
<ul class="list-inline">
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Support</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Privacy</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Terms of Service</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Contact</a>
</li>
</ul>
</div>
<div class="col-4 text-end">
<p class="mb-0">
&copy; 2022 - <a href="dashboard-default.html" class="text-muted">Spark</a>
</p>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>

```

```

<svg width="0" height="0" style="position:absolute">
<defs>
<symbol viewBox="0 0 512 512" id="ion-ios-pulse-strong">
<path
d="M448 273.001c-21.27 0-39.296 13.999-45.596 32.999h-38.857l-28.361-85.417a15.999 15.999 0
0 0-15.183-10.956c-.112 0-.224 0-.335.004a15.997 15.997 0 0 0-15.049 11.588l-44.484 155.262-
52.353-314.108C206.535 54.893 200.333 48 192 48s-13.693 5.776-15.525 13.135L115.496
306H16v31.999h112c7.348 0 13.75-5.003 15.525-12.134l45.368-182.177 51.324 307.94c1.229 7.377
7.397 11.92 14.864 12.344.308.018.614.028.919.028 7.097 0 13.406-3.701 15.381-10.594l49.744-
173.617 15.689 47.252A16.001 16.001 0 0 0 352 337.999h51.108C409.973 355.999 427.477 369 448
369c26.511 0 48-22.492 48-49 0-26.509-21.489-46.999-48-46.999z">
</path>
</symbol>
</defs>
</svg>
<script src="js/app.js"></script>

```

```
</body>
```

```
</html>
```

user-add.php

```
<?php
```

```
include_once("connections/connections.php");
$con = connection();
```

```
if(!isset($_SESSION)){
    session_start();
}
```

```
if(!isset($_SESSION['UserLogin'])){
    echo header("Location: index.php");
}else{
```

```
if(isset($_POST['submit_input2'])){
```

```
    $username = $_POST['username'];
    $password = $_POST['password'];
    $access = $_POST['access'];
```

```
    $sql = "INSERT INTO `jeepq_users`(`username`, `password`, `access`) VALUES
('{$username}', '{$password}', '{$access}')";
    $con->query($sql) or die($con->error);
    echo header("Location: user-details.php"); //redirects page to avoid double entry uploads
}
}
```

```
?>
```

```
<?php include "header.php";?>
```

```
</nav>
```

```
<main class="content">
```

```
<div class="container-fluid">
```

```
<div class="header">
```

```
<h1 class="header-title">
```

```
Add New Subscribers
```

```
</h1>
```

```
<nav aria-label="breadcrumb">
```

```
<ol class="breadcrumb">
```

```
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Home</a></li>
```

```
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Accounts</a></li>
```

```

<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="passenger-details.php">Passenger List</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item active" aria-current="page">Add New Subscribers</li>
</ol>
</nav>
</div>

```

```

<div class="card">
<div class="card-header">

<h5 class="card-title mb-0">Private info</h5>
</div>
<div class="card-body">
<form action="" method="post">
  <?php if($_SESSION['Access']==='administrator'){?>
  <div class="row">
    <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
      <label>Username</label>
      <input type="text" class="form-control" name="username" id="username">
    </div>
  </div>
  <div class="row">
    <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
      <label>Password</label>
      <input type="text" class="form-control" name="password" id="password">
    </div>
  </div>
  <div class="row">
    <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
      <label>Access</label>
      <select class="form-select flex-grow-1" name="access" id="select">
        <option value="">Select...</option>
        <option value="administrator">administrator</option>
        <option value="user">user</option>
      </select>
    </div>
  </div>
  <input type="button" class="btn btn-primary" onclick="document.location='user-
details.php'" value="Back">
<button type="submit" class="btn btn-primary" name="submit_input2" value="Submit
Form">Submit</button>
  <?php }else{?>
  <h6 class="card-title mb-0">You are not allowed to access this page. </h6><br>
  <input type="button" class="btn btn-primary"
onclick="document.location='index.php'" value="Home">
  <?php } ?>
</form>

</div>

```

```

</div>

</div>

</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</main>
<footer class="footer">
<div class="container-fluid">
<div class="row text-muted">
<div class="col-8 text-start">
<ul class="list-inline">
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Support</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Privacy</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Terms of Service</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Contact</a>
</li>
</ul>
</div>
<div class="col-4 text-end">
<p class="mb-0">
&copy; 2022 - <a href="dashboard-default.html" class="text-muted">Spark</a>
</p>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>

```

```

<svg width="0" height="0" style="position:absolute">
<defs>
<symbol viewBox="0 0 512 512" id="ion-ios-pulse-strong">
<path
d="M448 273.001c-21.27 0-39.296 13.999-45.596 32.999h-38.857l-28.361-85.417a15.999 15.999 0
0 0-15.183-10.956c-.112 0-.224 0-.335.004a15.997 15.997 0 0 0-15.049 11.588l-44.484 155.262-
52.353-314.108C206.535 54.893 200.333 48 192 48s-13.693 5.776-15.525 13.135L115.496
306H16v31.999h112c7.348 0 13.75-5.003 15.525-12.134l45.368-182.177 51.324 307.94c1.229 7.377
7.397 11.92 14.864 12.344.308.018.614.028.919.028 7.097 0 13.406-3.701 15.381-10.594l49.744-
173.617 15.689 47.252A16.001 16.001 0 0 0 352 337.999h51.108C409.973 355.999 427.477 369 448
369c26.511 0 48-22.492 48-49 0-26.509-21.489-46.999-48-46.999z">
</path>

```

```

</symbol>
</defs>
</svg>
<script src="js/app.js"></script>

<script type="text/javascript">
function yesnoCheck(that) {
  if (that.value == "Driver") {
    alert("Input your Jeepney's plate number.");
    document.getElementById("ifYes").style.display = "block";
  } else {
    document.getElementById("ifYes").style.display = "none";
  }
}
</script>
</body>

</html>

```

user-delete.php

```

<?php

include_once("connections/connections.php");
$con = connection();

//echo $_POST['IDdelete'];
//print_r($_POST);

if(!isset($_SESSION)){
  session_start();
}

if(!isset($_SESSION['UserLogin'])){
  echo header("Location: index.php");
}else{

if(isset($_POST['delete_button2'])){

  $iddelete = $_POST['IDdelete2'];
  $sql = "DELETE FROM jeepq_users WHERE id ='$iddelete'";
  $con->query($sql) or die ($con->error);

  echo header("Location: user-details.php");
}
}
?>

```

user-details.php

```

<?php
//checks if the session already set
if(!isset($_SESSION)){
    session_start();
}

if(!isset($_SESSION['UserLogin'])){
    echo header("Location: login.php");
}

include_once("connections/connections.php"); //para hnd paulit ulit na include
$con = connection(); //requesting connection to database

$sql = "SELECT * FROM jeepq_users ORDER BY id DESC";
$jeepq_users = $con->query($sql) or die($con->error);
$row = $jeepq_users->fetch_assoc(); // retrieves 1 only (need loop statements)
//print_r($row); //built in print array
// do{ //retrieves all $students->fetch_assoc() data
//     echo $row['first_name']." ".$row['last_name']."<br/>";
// }while($row = $students->fetch_assoc()); //execute code while statement is still true
//! + tab

?>

<?php include "header.php";?>

</nav>
<main class="content">
<div class="container-fluid">

<div class="header">
<h1 class="header-title">
Subscribers
</h1>
<nav aria-label="breadcrumb">
<ol class="breadcrumb">
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Home</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="#">Accounts</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item active" aria-current="page">Subscribers</li>
</ol>
</nav>
</div>
<div class="row">

<div class="col-12">
<div class="card">
<div class="card-header">
<h5 class="card-title">Subscriber List</h5>

```

```

<h6 class="card-subtitle text-muted">
<?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
<button class="btn btn-primary" onclick="document.location='user-add.php'">Add</button> -
Register new passenger information.
<?php } ?>
</h6>
</div>
<div class="card-body">
    <?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
<table id="datatables-reponsive" class="table table-striped" style="width:100%">
<thead>
<tr>
<th>User Name</th>
<th>Access</th>
<th>Actions</th>
</tr>
</thead>
<tbody>

<?php do{ ?>
<tr>
<td><?php echo $row['username'];?></td>
<td><?php echo $row['access'];?></td>
<td>
<a href="user-details-view.php?IDview=<?php echo $row['ID'];?>"><i class="align-middle fas fa-fw fa-eye"></i></a>
    <?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
<a href="user-edit.php?IDedit=<?php echo $row['ID'];?>"><i class="align-middle fas fa-fw fa-pen"></i></a>
<a href="user-details-view.php?IDview=<?php echo $row['ID'];?>"><i class="align-middle fas fa-fw fa-trash"></i></a></td>
<?php } ?></td>
</tr>

    <?php }while($row = $jeepq_users->fetch_assoc()) ?>
</tbody>
</table>
    <?php }else{?>
    <h6 class="card-title mb-0">You are not allowed to access this page. </h6><br>
    <input type="button" class="btn btn-primary" onclick="document.location='index.php'"
value="Home">
    <?php } ?>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</main>
<footer class="footer">
<div class="container-fluid">

```

```

<div class="row text-muted">
<div class="col-8 text-start">
<ul class="list-inline">
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Support</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Privacy</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Terms of Service</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Contact</a>
</li>
</ul>
</div>
<div class="col-4 text-end">
<p class="mb-0">
&copy; 2022 - <a href="dashboard-default.html" class="text-muted">Spark</a>
</p>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>

```

```

<svg width="0" height="0" style="position:absolute">
<defs>
<symbol viewBox="0 0 512 512" id="ion-ios-pulse-strong">
<path
d="M448 273.001c-21.27 0-39.296 13.999-45.596 32.999h-38.857l-28.361-85.417a15.999 15.999 0
0 0-15.183-10.956c-.112 0-.224 0-.335.004a15.997 15.997 0 0 0-15.049 11.588l-44.484 155.262-
52.353-314.108C206.535 54.893 200.333 48 192 48s-13.693 5.776-15.525 13.135L115.496
306H16v31.999h112c7.348 0 13.75-5.003 15.525-12.134l45.368-182.177 51.324 307.94c1.229 7.377
7.397 11.92 14.864 12.344.308.018.614.028.919.028 7.097 0 13.406-3.701 15.381-10.594l49.744-
173.617 15.689 47.252A16.001 16.001 0 0 0 352 337.999h51.108C409.973 355.999 427.477 369 448
369c26.511 0 48-22.492 48-49 0-26.509-21.489-46.999-48-46.999z">
</path>
</symbol>
</defs>
</svg>
<script src="js/app.js"></script>

```

```

<script>
document.addEventListener("DOMContentLoaded", function() {
// Datatables Responsive
$("#datatables-reponsive").DataTable({
responsive: true
});

```

```
});
</script>
</body>

</html>
```

user-details-view.php

```
<?php
//checks if the session already set
include_once("connections/connections.php"); //para hnd paulit ulit na include
$con = connection(); //requesting connection to database

if(!isset($_SESSION)){
    session_start();
}

if(!isset($_SESSION['UserLogin'])){
    echo header("Location: index.php");
}else{

$idview = $_GET['IDview'];

$sql = "SELECT * FROM jeepq_users WHERE id = '$idview'";
$students = $con->query($sql) or die($con->error);
$row = $students->fetch_assoc(); // retrieves 1 only (need loop statements)

}

// if(isset($_POST['update_input'])){
//
//     $fname = $_POST['firstname'];
//     $lname = $_POST['lastname'];
//     $birthday = $_POST['birthday'];
//     $gender = $_POST['gender'];
//     $location = $_POST['location'];
//     $number = '+63' . $_POST['number'];
//
//     $sql = "UPDATE jeepq_list SET first_name='$fname', last_name='$lname', gender='$gender',
//     birth_day='$birthday', location='$location', cell_number='$number' WHERE id='$idedit'";
//     $con->query($sql) or die($con->error);
//
//     echo header("Location: details.php?IDview=".$idedit); //redirects page to avoid double entry
//     uploads
// }

?>
```

```

<?php include "header.php";?>

</nav>
<main class="content">
<div class="container-fluid">

<div class="header">
<h1 class="header-title">
View Subscriber Details
</h1>
<nav aria-label="breadcrumb">
<ol class="breadcrumb">
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Home</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Accounts</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="passenger-details.php">Subscribers</a></li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item active" aria-current="page">View Subscriber Details</li>
</ol>
</nav>
</div>

<div class="card">
  <div class="card-header">

    <h5 class="card-title mb-0">Private info</h5>
  </div>
  <div class="card-body">
    <form action="user-delete.php" method="post">
      <?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
        <div class="row">
          <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
            <label>First name</label>
            <input type="text" class="form-control" name="username" id="username" value="<?php
echo $row['username'];?>" readonly>
          </div>
        </div>
        <div class="row">
          <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
            <label>Last name</label>
            <input type="password" class="form-control" name="password" id="password"
value="<?php echo $row['password'];?>" readonly>
          </div>
        </div>
        <div class="row">
          <div class="mb-3 col-md-3">
            <label>Access</label>
            <input type="text" class="form-control" name="access" id="access" value="<?php echo
$row['access'];?>" readonly>
          </div>
        </div>
      </div>
    </form>
  </div>
</div>

```

```

    </div>
    <input type="button" class="btn btn-primary" onclick="document.location='user-
details.php'" value="Back">
    <?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
    <input type="button" class="btn btn-primary" onclick="document.location='user-
edit.php?IDedit=<?php echo $row['ID'];?>" value="Edit">
    <button type="submit" class="btn btn-primary" name="delete_button2">Delete</button>
    <input type="hidden" name="IDdelete2" value="<?php echo $row['ID'];?>">
    <?php } ?>
    <?php }else{?>
    <h6 class="card-title mb-0">You are not allowed to access this page. </h6><br>
    <input type="button" class="btn btn-primary" onclick="document.location='index.php'"
value="Home">
    <?php } ?>

</form>

</div>
</div>

```

```

</div>

</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</main>
<footer class="footer">
<div class="container-fluid">
<div class="row text-muted">
<div class="col-8 text-start">
<ul class="list-inline">
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Support</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Privacy</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Terms of Service</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Contact</a>
</li>
</ul>
</div>
<div class="col-4 text-end">

```

```

<p class="mb-0">
&copy; 2022 - <a href="dashboard-default.html" class="text-muted">Spark</a>
</p>
</div>

```

```

<svg width="0" height="0" style="position:absolute">
<defs>
<symbol viewBox="0 0 512 512" id="ion-ios-pulse-strong">
<path
d="M448 273.001c-21.27 0-39.296 13.999-45.596 32.999h-38.857l-28.361-85.417a15.999 15.999 0
0 0-15.183-10.956c-.112 0-.224 0-.335.004a15.997 15.997 0 0 0-15.049 11.588l-44.484 155.262-
52.353-314.108C206.535 54.893 200.333 48 192 48s-13.693 5.776-15.525 13.135L115.496
306H16v31.999h112c7.348 0 13.75-5.003 15.525-12.134l45.368-182.177 51.324 307.94c1.229 7.377
7.397 11.92 14.864 12.344.308.018.614.028.919.028 7.097 0 13.406-3.701 15.381-10.594l49.744-
173.617 15.689 47.252A16.001 16.001 0 0 0 352 337.999h51.108C409.973 355.999 427.477 369 448
369c26.511 0 48-22.492 48-49 0-26.509-21.489-46.999-48-46.999z">
</path>
</symbol>
</defs>
</svg>
<script src="js/app.js"></script>

</body>

</html>

```

user-edit.php

```

<?php

include_once("connections/connections.php");
$con = connection();

if(!isset($_SESSION)){
    session_start();
}

if(!isset($_SESSION['UserLogin'])){
    echo header("Location: index.php");
}else{

    if(!isset($_SESSION['Access']) && $_SESSION['Access']=="administrator"){
        echo header("Location: index.php");
    }
}

```

```

$idedit=$_GET['IDedit'];
$sql = "SELECT * FROM jeepq_users WHERE id = '$idedit'";
$students = $con->query($sql) or die($con->error);
$row = $students->fetch_assoc(); // retrieves 1 only (need loop statements)

```

```

if(isset($_POST['update_input2'])){

```

```

    $username = $_POST['username'];
    $password = $_POST['password'];
    $access = $_POST['access'];

```

```

    $sql = "UPDATE jeepq_users SET username='$username', password='$password',
access='$access' WHERE id='$idedit'";
    $con->query($sql) or die($con->error);

```

```

    echo header("Location: user-details-view.php?IDview=".$idedit); //redirects page to avoid
double entry uploads

```

```

}
}
?>

```

```

<?php include "header.php";?>

```

```

</nav>

```

```

<main class="content">

```

```

<div class="container-fluid">

```

```

<div class="header">

```

```

<h1 class="header-title">

```

```

Edit Passenger Details

```

```

</h1>

```

```

<nav aria-label="breadcrumb">

```

```

<ol class="breadcrumb">

```

```

<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Home</a></li>

```

```

<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.php">Accounts</a></li>

```

```

<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="passenger-details.php">Subscribers</a></li>

```

```

<li class="breadcrumb-item active" aria-current="page">Edit Subscriber Details</li>

```

```

</ol>

```

```

</nav>

```

```

</div>

```

```

<div class="card">

```

```

<div class="card-header">

```

```

<h5 class="card-title mb-0">Private info</h5>

```

```

</div>

```

```

<div class="card-body">

```

```

    <form action="" method="post">

```

```

<?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?>
<div class="row">
  <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
    <label>Username</label>
    <input type="text" class="form-control" name="username" id="username"
value="<?php echo $row['username'];?>">
  </div>
</div>
<div class="row">
  <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
    <label>Password</label>
    <input type="text" class="form-control" name="password" id="password"
    <?php if($_SESSION['Access']=='administrator'){?> value="<?php echo
$row['password'];?>" <?php } ?>>
  </div>
</div>
<div class="row">
  <div class="mb-3 col-md-6">
    <label>Access</label>
    <select class="form-select flex-grow-1" name="access" id="select">
      <option value="">Select...</option>
      <option value="administrator" <?php echo ($row['access']=='administrator')?
'selected':";?>>administrator</option>
      <option value="user" <?php echo ($row['access']=='user')?
'selected':";?>>user</option>
    </select>
  </div>
</div>
  <input type="button" class="btn btn-primary" onclick="document.location='user-
details.php?IDview=<?php echo $row['ID'];?>" value="Back">
  <input type="submit" class="btn btn-primary" name="update_input2"
value="Update">
  <?php }else{?>
  <h6 class="card-title mb-0">You are not allowed to access this page. </h6><br>
  <input type="button" class="btn btn-primary"
onclick="document.location='index.php'" value="Home">
  <?php } ?>
</form>

</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</main>
<footer class="footer">

```

```

<div class="container-fluid">
<div class="row text-muted">
<div class="col-8 text-start">
<ul class="list-inline">
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Support</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Privacy</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Terms of Service</a>
</li>
<li class="list-inline-item">
<a class="text-muted" href="#">Contact</a>
</li>
</ul>
</div>
<div class="col-4 text-end">
<p class="mb-0">
&copy; 2022 - <a href="dashboard-default.html" class="text-muted">Spark</a>
</p>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>

```

```

<svg width="0" height="0" style="position:absolute">
<defs>
<symbol viewBox="0 0 512 512" id="ion-ios-pulse-strong">
<path
d="M448 273.001c-21.27 0-39.296 13.999-45.596 32.999h-38.857l-28.361-85.417a15.999 15.999 0
0 0-15.183-10.956c-.112 0-.224 0-.335.004a15.997 15.997 0 0 0-15.049 11.588l-44.484 155.262-
52.353-314.108C206.535 54.893 200.333 48 192 48s-13.693 5.776-15.525 13.135L115.496
306H16v31.999h112c7.348 0 13.75-5.003 15.525-12.134l45.368-182.177 51.324 307.94c1.229 7.377
7.397 11.92 14.864 12.344.308.018.614.028.919.028 7.097 0 13.406-3.701 15.381-10.594l49.744-
173.617 15.689 47.252A16.001 16.001 0 0 0 352 337.999h51.108C409.973 355.999 427.477 369 448
369c26.511 0 48-22.492 48-49 0-26.509-21.489-46.999-48-46.999z">
</path>
</symbol>
</defs>
</svg>
<script src="js/app.js"></script>

</body>

</html>

```